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HSbooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

Intermediate Standards Impact Report

Deliverable

4.3

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EPE	External pool of experts
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
WG	Working Group
TC	Technical Committee

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Executive Summary

*The HSbooster.eu project kicked off in April 2022, soon after the launch of the European Standardisation strategies issued in February 2022, to which it is aligned. HSbooster.eu aims to increase the **impact of European standardisation** resulting from H2020 & Horizon Europe Research & Innovation projects by designing, launching, and managing a dedicated “booster-type” initiative.*

*Year 2 of the project it is time to reflect on the significant impact of the HSBooster project and the Standards Catalogue, which engaged European projects with an NSB and/or TC through active participation in European and global standardization initiatives. **Phase I of 35** completed projects reports measure **126**, involving standardisation with **15** collaborating with NSB and/or TC to address Standard and TC-related matters, and **20** focusing on standardisation strategy.*

HSbooster.eu monitoring will continue, and the process will stay open so that improvements can be made as needed. Deliverable D4.3 focuses on the development of a highly engaged community of European Standardisation. The process includes experts, results, problem-solving, an evaluation module, and a feedback system for applicants.

*We are now experiencing a process driven open call system with an impact of **250** Automated Services, Proactive Services **103**, Premium Services **117**, engaging Experts **181**, **275** participants at **4** Proactive webinars, **5226** page views of online training academy content, **15** contributions of experts with collaborations with **6** SDOs on series of webinar. Registered experts are linked with registered projects to provide them with guidance on standards in their particular domain, and projects have access to fast, free, automated online standards information services.*

*Impact to policy, over **20** projects are expected to join an ecosystem aimed at fostering communication between policy makers, standardization bodies, and experts, particularly SMEs. SDO, policy makers, and projects will be invited to participate, allowing interaction beyond the HSBooster project duration.*

1 Introduction

HSbooster.eu. offers expert services to European projects to help them engage with Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and Technical Committees (TCs). This engagement is crucial for aligning project outcomes with existing and developing standards, ensuring relevance and applicability in their respective fields. As reported during Deliverable **D4.1**, the focus is on the premium services where such an impact could be gathered and reported. Therefore, **D4.3** presents a monitoring strategy for the project's engagement process, enabling partners to identify more progress and status impacted by HSbooster.eu. It documents new Experts, Standards activities attended, extended premium services deep dive workshop series, CEN Workshop Agreements, and training of Standards leaders.

The goal of Deliverable **D4.3**, as stated in the Description of Action, is to provide an “Intermediate Standards Impact Report for Projects Onboarded, SDOs engaged, Standards documents contributed to, event reporting, At the time this report is due, keep track of the results and problems, make an evaluation module and a feedback system for applicants, and come up with a standard operating process.

The **Expert Advisory Group’s (EAG)** expertise and broader understanding of the standards domain are crucial for delivering the most impactful piece to the HSBooster project, which will be expanded under **sections 3, 4 and 5**. We have received a total of 31 recommendations from the 35 reports that have been reviewed by EAG.

Additionally, one of the vital impacts that the HSBooster.eu project can demonstrate in this report is the **standards catalogue**. It will be demonstrated in **Section 5**. This would also aid in influencing the standards that are pertinent to our projects. Given the diverse nature of emerging technologies, multiple committees could benefit from our input. This report provides an overview of the impact of the HSbooster.eu standards catalogue and presents the results of the practical guidance and support offered. It also emphasizes the proactive measures to engage with the most appropriate SDO or WG to guide the projects toward the most promising standardization pathways.

1.1 High-level overview of Impact in M24

Since the start of the project, **117** projects and **181** experts have been contracted and monitored through direct engagement in the Premium Service program. The participants are Standards Experts and actively engage in SDOs at SC, TC, and WG Standardization levels. The HSbooster.eu service consists of one-on-one and one-to-many correspondence and includes standards and standardisation mapping and matchmaking consultancy. The project has been in touch with a number of NSBs, working groups, standards communities, and European and international standard developers. HSbooster.eu is part of a large network of standard developers. It is critical to ensure collaboration and knowledge exchange between HSbooster.eu and standardisation stakeholders in order to achieve long-term impact.

Measurements of Impact

- **The service matrix:** From identifying the open call topics based on EU standardization Code of Practice priorities to designing, piloting, and revising the three HSbooster.eu

services, as impacted, we have a smooth open call with impact **250** on Automated Services, Proactive Services **103**, and Premium Services **117**.

- **Engagement with Standards Development Organizations:** Projects engage with Standards Development Organizations and Technical Committees to align project goals and activities with existing and developing standards, ensuring relevance and applicability in their respective fields.
- **The services:** Over **181** standardisation experts recruited, ranked and ready to deliver premium services to projects.
- **CEN Workshop Agreements:** HSbooster offers CEN Workshop Agreements services to facilitate standardization in various sectors, focusing on projects recommended for premium services. They have identified 2 opportunities for these services, supporting NanoMECommons and Ashcycle projects, based on their consultancy service.
- **HSbooster Training Academy:** has **15** experts contributing to its services, including a framework for webinars focused on standardization and presentations for European NSBs, ISO/IEC community, and EC officers.
- **A growing community** of standardisation experts and R&I projects that are actively involved in augmenting the project input into the standardisation service facility that is catering to various organisations and projects. Another direct impact has been the EPE's community, which includes future members of the initial group for invitations to other projects such as StandICT and the FOREST Group.
- **Impact of the EPE and EAG on the projects:** The EAG provides external advice to ensure an international project profile, capturing important data and establishing mechanisms to support standardization experts.
- **The HSbooster.eu standards catalogue:** The HSbooster.eu standards catalogue was implemented, and the results of the practical guidance given by the experts are shown in Annex 4. Phase I of 35 completed project reports indicated that 126 mentions of standardisation. It also emphasizes proactive measures, engaging with the most relevant SDO or WG, directing the projects towards the correct standardization paths that would have the most significant potential for success.

2 Impact of HSbooster.eu services

The HSbooster.eu service matrix Delivery Machine (Automated, Proactive and Premium Services), service, aims to address EU standardisation Code of Practice priorities by designing, piloting, and revising three services. The platform's procedures, detailed in D2.2 (M14) and the revised service matrix in D4.2, represent the significant impact of the project's premium services.

Table 1 – Summary of HSbooster.eu KPIs services

Description	M30 KPI	M24 Status
Service facility serving projects/organisations	1,000 projects /organisations served	530(sum of Services below)
Automated services delivered	250	250+
Proactive Services delivered	250	163+
Premium Services delivered	300	117 premium services: 11 applications being processed 35 ongoing services 71 complete services
Open calls delivered	5 open calls	1 continuous open call replaced the original plan.
Experts contractualised	250	181 recruited and ranked 76 of which delivering services
HSbooster.eu services Webinars	8 of 14 (6 of which dedicated to training)	4
Participation at 3rd party events	20	15

The table below summarises the three levels of service offered by HSbooster.eu. The services are, by design, incremental in terms of engagement, interaction, and potential impact. Each service can impact on each other. For example, an automated service may act as an engagement hook on which a proactive service (mapping activity) or premium service may occur. However, the services are not necessarily directly connected, and it is possible for a project only to receive one service type.

Table 2 – Hsbooster.eu Service Delivery

Service	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Duration
Automated (T3.1)	The end-user accesses the service from the FAQ or Help Desk points on the website	Browse/download info available on the website. In case the session closes with FAQs or intervention of the bot, skip to Step 5	The end-user wishes to enter a one-on-one session with one HSbooster.eu staff member and register her/him self to the community	The live session takes place	From a few hours up to 1 week

Proactive (T3.2)	Desktop research to identify groups H2020/HE projects and match them to relevant standards' areas and at least one candidate SDO	Proactive to discussions with at both the projects of and the SDO	Deliver a webinar with the Projects and the SDOs to outline the landscape and map standards potential.	Monitor the development of the interaction for up to 1 month	Up to 1 month
Premium (T3.3)	The end-user (facility) wishing to apply to the Open Call completes an online, detailed application form to HSbooster.eu	On a weekly basis the applications are assessed for eligibility	The Expert is selected from the EPE and the end-user is informed & a dialogue starts.	The service is carried out with contributions from the EPE Expert and the HSbooster.eu staff	Up to 3 months

2.1 Support Services - Automated Services

The Support Services sections illustrate the influence of the services and demonstrate the outcomes of associated tools employed with EPE and users. The automated service aims to provide guidance and support to steer research results of projects towards the most promising standardisation pathway. The KPI of 250 services has been surpassed.

By design, the automated service provides freely accessible information via different channels available on the website and one-on-one sessions with HSbooster.eu staff. Therefore, as a new project, a more outwardly facing strategy was employed as part of the Automated services.

Table 3 – Automated service overview

<i>Automated service</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>No. at M19</i>
Direct interaction	Exchange via email and/or conference calls and/or meetings with projects promoting HSbooster.eu services.	260
Helpdesk page & FaQ pages(s)	Web page(s), providing assistance and guidance to HSbooster.eu's resources and services users. The helpdesk also includes a contact email info@hsbooster.eu.	1,800 visits
Chatbot	The chat feature is available on the HSbooster.eu homepage. It provides info on services and standardisation using conversational AI technology to simulate a human dialogue and resolve queries.	175 users
Standards Orientation Tool	The SOT is designed to guide projects and consortia writing proposals to create informed standardisation strategies. They launched in late November 2023.	3 users

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2.2 Support Services - Proactive Services

The proactive service, **Task 3.2**, is delivered through engagement between HSbooster.eu partners, experts, and Horizon projects. The service consists of one-on-one or one-to-many contact and includes standards and standardisation mappings and matchmaking consultancy. The proactive service was launched in month ten and will run through the remainder of the project. **The KPI of Proactive Service 250 delivered 163+.**

The purpose is to help projects identify relevant standards and standardisation bodies depending on the technical field including TCs, SCs and WGs by:

- Giving introductory information about basic terms, processes and structures within standardisation and benefits of using standards for researchers, CEOs, SMEs etc.
- Facilitating contact with an NSB or SDO.
- Providing access to up to 3 standards per project if relevant and needed.
- Introducing the HSbooster.eu premium service and providing a gentle push towards registration if interested.
- Identifying initial standardisation areas of relevance for the project.

The projects are mainly identified via:

- Desktop research on CORDIS database with all current R&I projects receiving funds from the EU Commission, using the extensive search function in the database as sorting mechanism.
- CCMCs (CEN-CENELEC Management Centre) annual screening of H2020 and Horizon Europe calls relevant for standardisation.
- Other projects that are highlighted/tipped about as part of an existing proactive service.
- Lists of existing projects within the European NSB community.
- Diverse set of information through standardisation news, scientific newsletters, web sites, press releases, etc.

The aim is to increase the European standardisation impact on **250** projects via proactive engagement between the projects, HSbooster.eu and/or appropriate SDOs.

Methodology and results: The activities in the proactive service consist of:

- Proactive contact to and one-to-on dialogue with selected Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects that have started or have recently finished.
- One-to-many dialogue and knowledge sharing through workshops and webinars

A total of **166** projects have been personally contacted in the proactive service via personalized, direct emails. The response to these emails has been approximately **23%**, i.e **39** projects have positively reacted to the personalized outreach from HSbooster.eu and

received a proactive service. Out of the **39** correspondences originating from personalized emails, **9** resulted in one-on-one calls, and the remaining 30 consisted of written communication via email.

In addition to emails, other methods have been used to attract people to the one-to-many webinars, e.g., LinkedIn campaigns.

When it comes to the one-to-many proactive service, , more than **64** projects participated in the proactive webinars. Since the initial proactive webinar did not include a headcount of project participants, the exact figure is unknown.

Approximately **103** proactive services have been given (**39** via one-to-one and **64+** one-to-many). **29** projects that received a proactive service regardless of its form also applied for and received a premium service.

One-to-one proactive services: The projects were given information about relevant technical committees and standards during the one-to-one conference calls. The dialogue was also initiated on how the projects can benefit from using other HSbooster services, particularly the Premium Service.

Many proactive services resulted in the agreement that the project will further investigate the HSbooster.eu website and other services manually. Out of the seven proactive one-to-one services, four have gone on to apply for the Premium Service.

One-to-many proactive services: During HSbooster.eu it became clear that an effective way of conducting the proactive service was via one-to-many proactive webinars.

The following are **requirements** that need to be met for a webinar to be classified as proactive:

- Horizon projects must be proactively contacted by HSbooster.eu with an invitation for the webinar. The invited projects should be selected based on their call and project topics, which should match the webinar topic.
- The webinars must contain key elements from the proactive service such as
 - identification of relevant technical committees,
 - identification of relevant standardisation areas of relevance for the projects,
 - facilitation of contact between projects and TCs e.g. by having the TCs give presentations and provide their contact details.
- There was an opportunity for the projects to engage with HSbooster.eu and the presenters during the webinar in order to answer any project specific questions.
- The webinars promoted other HSbooster.eu tools and services, in particular the Premium Service by explaining the “who, why and how” for projects.

By December 2023, a total of four proactive webinars were held by HSbooster.eu. Their focus has been on key EU priorities: **Artificial Intelligence, Plastics recycling, Health and Cybersecurity**.

The KPI of HSbooster.eu services Webinars 8 of 14 (6 of which dedicated to training): delivered 4.

Table 4 – Webinars, Topic Participants and Projects Overview

Webinar Topic_Date	Registrations	Participants	Projects
AI_19 Dec 2022	154	98	Not registered
Plastic_27 Apr 2023	83	47	28
Health_7 Sep 2023	100	68	24
Cybersecurity_17 Oct 2023	95	62	12
Total	432	275	64

Six additional proactive webinars will be planned and conducted in 2024.

Impact of proactive service – summary: Between M10 and M21 several projects have been contacted as part of the proactive services. More than **103** of these projects have received a proactive service in HSbooster.eu, however, in reality, the number is most likely higher as the number of projects in the first proactive webinar was not registered.

The key impacts of the proactive service includes:

- Projects increase their knowledge about standards and standardisation within their projects’ focal area. This gives projects the opportunity to use relevant standards in their projects and interact with relevant technical committees either directly or during the proactive webinars.
- Projects become aware of the opportunities given by HSbooster.eu. There is a clear link between the proactive and premium services, however, projects also become aware of other tools and opportunities such as the Standardisation Orientation Tool and Training Academy.

Additionally, some of the projects that have received a proactive service, have applied for or received a premium service as well. Therefore, the impact from proactive service is two-fold. Out of the **103** proactive services, **29** projects have applied to the premium service. In some cases, the proactive services inspire projects to apply for the premium service, and in other cases projects receiving a premium service benefit from participating in a proactive webinar. This shows the close link between the different types of services in HSbooster and how the **impact** can be multiplied by combining more than one service.

The text above details how many projects HSbooster.eu have been directly impacted by HSbooster via the proactive service. However, many of the projects that receive the proactive service are also participating in other projects. Thus, a positive spillover from the proactive service is likely to occur, resulting in a cascading effect.

2.3 Support Services - Premium Services

The HSbooster.eu project offers a premium service through a continuous open call process for standardisation experts and projects, providing dedicated and specialised assistance to projects in their standardisation efforts.

The KPI of Premium Service 300: 117 delivered, 11 applications being processed 35 ongoing services 71 complete services.

The KPI of Experts contractualised 250: 181 recruited and ranked, 76 of which delivering services.

The original format for each service saw experts delivering each service over a period of two effective working days (16 hours) which was remunerated at €800 per service (€400 per EWD). A total budget of €400,000 of Linked Third Party Costs is allocated to the delivery of Premium services.

2.3.1 Evolution of the Premium Services

In Y2 of the project the consortium is exploring how to diversify the Premium service to ensure that the originally defined services continuously evolve. This is based on the continuous feedback which is collected both from the External Pool of Experts (EPE) and projects. In the table below we provide a brief overview of the evolution of the services. This is based on feedback from EPE who have delivered services in M12-18:

- We believe the original format of 2 PDs per service is often too short for the expert to provide the desired impact. Therefore, we extended premium services whereby experts are now able to request an extension of up to 6 PDs based on project objectives and required standardisation knowledge.
- Based on the positive impact of the one-to-many Proactive service format and specific requests from clusters of projects, we proposed “deep dive workshops” providing in-depth information on standardisation to groups of projects.
- Finally, with €80,000 of the external cost budget dedicated to facilitating projects to engage in standardisation, we noticed a demand for financial support for projects to develop CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA).

A full overview of the lessons learned in delivering services and how services evolve will be provided in D3.2 (M28).

Table 5 – lessons learned in delivering services

Service	Target projects	Description
Extended Premium services	All projects	Provision of longer terms support to projects for up to 6 person days. Based on Y1 feedback from both experts and projects, longer-term support was specifically requested.
Deep dive workshop series	Projects grouped by specific calls, or projects funded through Joint Undertakings, EU Innovation Centre and EU Missions	Series of 3 workshops based on needs of target projects. Workshops can cover different topics based on the standardisation-related needs. EPE will be recruited to deliver these workshops. This activity is being piloted with EIC projects on the topic of Engineered Living Materials.

CEN Workshop Agreements	Projects with specific goal of CWA	Service providing technical input and engagement support. Funding of up to €10,000 to cover related CWA costs can be offered too through external costs. In considering applications, we will consider the overall CWA costs, duration, expected impact alignment with EU strategic goals.
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2.3.2 Single project Premium services

In this section we provide examples and testimonials on how expert input via the premium services has directly impacted on projects. We consider common types of support that are requested by projects.

- Standards as a vehicle for the valorisation of R&I project results

REFLECT AFRICA - Renewable energies for Africa: Effective valorization of agri-food wastes

Participation in HSBooster was an asset as it provided a debate on technological solutions that could be useful for the project to achieve and have a greater impact on the overall results. The service made it possible to debate with all relevant partners the best support they could provide, as well as to define the area of action. Participating in this program gave us a new perspective on the importance of awareness-raising as a gateway to securing innovative technology and privileged access to emerging markets. Also, it was really enlightening to understand how standards can be a real tool in what regards all the project lifecycle, namely envisaging the wide spreading of the project results and scale-up.

Elsa Nunes, IrRADIARE

- Standards landscape analysis

A total of **71** experts have reviewed and indicated that they have provided a mapping of the standardisation landscape. This can aid projects to plan their strategy more effectively. This may include understanding how to comply with regulations and also guidance on which standards projects should adopt.

CyberSEAS - Cyber Securing Energy dAta Services

Expert: Wolfgang Ziegler, z-rands

CyberSEAS focusses on bolstering the cybersecurity of European electrical power energy systems. A key goal is to define a certification, standardisation and data exchange approach that outperforms current strategies.

“The interaction with Wolfgang, an expert with over 45 years of experience was instrumental for our project to navigate the intricate landscape of standards applicable to our domain. The guidance not only clarified the current standardisation landscape but also aided in cementing the standardisation strategy, notably the incorporation of standards like IEC 62443. One of the main challenges we faced was discerning the most fitting standards for critical infrastructure contexts. HSbooster's expertise illuminated the path for us, culminating in a tailored plan for integrating these standards into CyberSEAS. Our regular interactions with their experts—marked by robust technical recommendations, practical conversations, and unfaltering guidance—have been one of the high points of this collaboration.”

Husseis Anas, IKERLAN & CyberSEAS

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SENTINEL - Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

Expert: Harshvardhan Pandit, Dublin City University

SENTINEL bridges the security and personal data protection gap for European SMEs/MEs, by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture and then applying disruptive Intelligence for Compliance. A project objective is to “Collaborate with standardisation bodies to ensure that all SENTINEL solutions, products and services are aligned and harmonized with regulations and EU standards”

“With Harshvardhan’s support we examined how SENTINEL solutions should align with regulations and EU standards. GDPR-CARPA requirements were therefore analysed and relevant current and upcoming standards identified. This included several relevant ISO standards that SENTINEL could consider adopting and implementing. Through the meetings we were able to plan our next steps and discuss various standardisation topics. We would also like to note the seamless process and user-friendly features of the HSbooster.eu online platform. The entire experience, from initial contact to the completion of the service, was efficient and well-organised.”

Siranush Akarmazyan, ITML & SENTINEL

GLASS - SinGLe Sign-on eGovernAnce paradigm based on a distributed file exchange network for Security, transparency, cost effectiveness and truSt

Expert - Panos Kudumakis, Consultant

The GLASS project provides applications, services, and standards to facilitate cross-border data, evidence and credential sharing between citizens, governments, public administrations, and businesses in Europe. With a dedicated standardisation WP and tasks, the project beneficiaries needed support to refine their plans.

"As our project GLASS is dedicated to improving cross-border data sharing through our identity wallet, we understood the paramount importance of standardisation. Entering the HSBooster, our expectations were high, but the support and the insights we gained not only met but surpassed those expectations. Our interaction with Panos Kudumakis provided us with unique perspectives and in-depth knowledge about the diverse standardisation landscape. We wholeheartedly recommend this program to any research project aiming to delve deep into the realm of standardisation."

Fabian Kirstein, Fraunhofer FOKUS & GLASS

- Contributing to the development of national standards

H2Value - Supporting the Regional Development of the Green Hydrogen Fuel Value Chain for Transportation in Estonia and Latvia

With the help of a consultant, we gained a better understanding of regulations and standards in the field of hydrogen. We dealt with the production-, distribution- and consumption of green hydrogen. The information obtained made it possible to plan the implementation of the green hydrogen value chain in a more focused manner through CEN/TC 350 (Sustainability of construction works). The information obtained has also provided an opportunity to contribute to the development of national standards in Estonia.

Jaanus Tamm, Tartu City Government

Houseful

Thanks to HSBooster, HOUSEFUL is in discussions are underway with The Catalonia Institute of Construction Technology, ITEC. ITEC is a key collaborator in methodology development, to engage more effectively in relevant normativization committees.

ITEC has a significant role and experience in certification in Catalonia and their status as a certification entity provides valuable support and insight to help HOUSEFUL influence committee decisions

- Participation at TCs/WGs

CIMPA's Involvement in CEN/TC 261

CIMPA plans to closely follow the developments in CEN/TC 261. This engagement is facilitated through LEYGATECH, a partner in CIMPA, which has been assigned as an expert in CEN/TC 261/SC4/WG10 via AFNOR (French NSB). LEYGATECH's role involves integrating knowledge about WG10 and upcoming standards into the CIMPA project, ensuring that the project remains informed and aligned with standardisation efforts.

AssureMOSS and ETSI TC CYBER Engagement

Following their Hsbooster.eu service, the AssureMOSS team presented at the ETSI TC CYBER meeting, CYBER#34, in Sophia Antipolis, enhancing their engagement in cybersecurity standardisation. As documented in CYBER(23)034044r1. This engagement provided an opportunity for the AssureMOSS team to align its activities with the ongoing work of ETSI TC CYBER, fostering relevant dialogue and potential collaboration.

AFC4Hydro

Topic: Hydropower technology

Participated in national and international technical committees, notably IEC TC4 WG33.

Attended a key meeting in Kunming, China, to contribute to the development of IEC 62882, focusing on integrating AFC4Hydro technologies into hydroturbines.

The project benefited from expertise gained through the HSBooster program, enhancing understanding of committee operations and decision-making.

HERCCULES and CEN TC on CO2 Capture and Storage An expert recommended that HERCCULES get involved in the new CEN TC focusing on “CO2 capture, transportation, utilisation, storage and carbon accounting.” A representative from partner EUCORE has been given contact details of the TC reference person at CEN for follow-up and involvement. This engagement is expected to aid in aligning the project's work with the emerging standards in this critical area.

PREMUROSA: Navigating Medical Device Standards: For the project PREMUROSA, the expert recommends reviewing standards such as the ISO 10993 series on the Biological Evaluation of Medical Devices and EN 12006-2 1998 on Non-active Surgical Implants. This review is aimed at ensuring the project's outcomes are in line with the established standards in the medical field.

- Contributing to existing standards

CS-Aware-NEXT

The whole HSBooster consultancy process with CS-AWARE NEXT went fluently and there was great support by the team of CS-AWARE NEXT to identify a suitable standardisation strategy for their envisioned project results, such as adding an extension to the OASIS STIX public repository and the inclusion of this extension in the official STIX OASIS standard.

iHELP

Focusses on healthcare data standards. iHELP is aligning with the FHIR standard, planning to propose extensions to FHIR through a structured process involving stakeholder engagement and formal steps within the FHIR working group.

2.3.3 Recommendation from Experts to the projects

This section contains a comprehensive summary of the perspectives of experts concerning the procedure by which they furnish recommendations as part of the premium services they offer for projects. We analyze the diverse forms of assistance that are frequently requested by initiatives, including:

Types of standards A readiness assessment is provided, which gives an indication of the starting points or evaluation of standardization as well. Recommendations on how to access standards and effectively engage with the standardization process to obtain the final deliverables.

Evaluation

This page provides information on recommendations provided by experts to projects.

[Go back to the Project Service Performance Page](#)

Type of standards readiness assessment provided

Information provided on standards & standardisation mapping landscape

Recommendations on accessing standards

Recommendations on standardisation deliverables

Recommendations on standardisation strategy and engagement

Figure 1 – Recommendation from Experts to the projects

2.3.4 Premium deep dive workshops and Impact

By delivering deep dive workshops to groups of projects, the booster can impact positively on larger groups or clusters of projects. We have observed that this need may come when addressing thematic areas where input from funded projects to standardisation activities is required or desirable but is not taking place. By establishing a practical role for the HSbooster to deliver workshops in which projects engage with EPE members, greater impact can be made in this area. Currently, 1 deep dive webinar series has been delivered while 5 others are in progress completed by June 2024).

Table 6 – Premium deep dive workshops

Group	Topic	Standards/TC	No. of projects	Impact	Status
EIC Engineered Living Materials projects	Living Materials	ISO LCA series	8	Projects at very low TRLs. Focus on projects becoming standard users Introduction on ISO LCA series in measuring Life Cycle Assessment as early as possible as this can help the innovators in choosing the best solutions.	Complete
SNS JU	6G Networks	3GPP, ETSI	30	3 workshops in cooperation with SNS-OPS CSA coordinating the RIAs and IAs of phase I, contribution to SNS standardisation roadmap.	Ongoing
NetworkNature	Nature based solutions	TC Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities	465 73	3 workshops to projects Feb-Sept including NetworkNature annual event.	Ongoing
MSCA (Marie-Sklodowska Curie Actions) unit (DG-EAC)	General	TBC	TBC	Increase awareness of standardisation for valorisation through workshops at MSCA NCP meeting (Jan) & MCCA Annual Conference (March).	Ongoing
EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu community interested in Pilot Building, standardisation and upscale of cloud-edge-IoT solutions	Cloud, Edge & IoT Continuum	Various energy, transport, mobility, e.g. ISO TC204	in 50	Standardisation panel at EC info day (Jan) World leading data and computing technologies (HORIZON-CL4-2024-DATA-01). Prep for proposal writing on standardisation. Concertation workshop (Apr) for ongoing projects and newly funded ones.	Ongoing

Int:NET	Energy Transition	TBC	5	Support to Int:NET to provide standardisation landscaping and strategy to projects.
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- CEN Workshop Agreements services

This service aims to facilitate standardisation efforts in various sectors, with a particular focus on the involvement of projects that have previously applied for a premium service and were recommended to join or initiate a CWA by the assigned HSbooster expert as a result of their consultancy service. HSbooster has at the moment recognised two opportunities for this type of services supporting the projects NanoMECommons and Ashcycle.

NanoMECommons and Standardisation in Nanomechanics

NanoMECommons is involved in organising a CWA titled "Harmonisation of EU-wide nanomechanics protocols and relevant data exchange procedures." The Italian Standardisation body is acting as the secretariat for this project. The project is currently in the preparatory phase, with the kick-off scheduled for the end of the year, and discussions ongoing with UNI regarding administrative steps.

HSbooster supports this project by providing financial assistance and expert advice, particularly in technical and dissemination aspects. This support is intended to help NanoMECommons in achieving its goal of establishing standardised nanomechanics protocols.

- Ashcycle's Participation in CWA Activities

Informed by HSBooster, Ashcycle has decided to participate in the existing CWA "Guidelines on Action Research for Large Scale Piloting," aligning with its project objectives. Furthermore, Ashcycle plans to initiate a new CWA focused on sequestration methodology in 2024. This decision is a strategic move to align their activities with broader standardisation efforts.

The support provided by HSbooster to these CWAs aims to assist in the development and implementation of standardisation processes. HSbooster's role involves financial backing and the provision of expertise to facilitate these projects. This support is intended to contribute to the effective development and dissemination of the CWAs, potentially influencing standardization in related fields.

"We are very satisfied with the services provided by HSBooster, and the cooperation with Ms. Dejana Milinkovics was very useful. Her expertise in standardization issues has not only strengthened but also enhanced our existing knowledge as a member of CEN/CENELEC and EOTA, especially with regard to the CEN Workshop on agreement (CWA). We appreciate the effort she has put into preparing presentations with valuable and up-to-date information. Based on the information provided by HSBooster, we have decided to participate in the ongoing CWA "Guidelines on Action Research for Large Scale Piloting" as they are in line with AshCycle's objectives. And for 2024, it is planned that our consortium will initiate a new CWA on sequestration methodology."

Vilma Ducman, ZAG & AshCycle

3 HSbooster.eu Training Academy

Supporting the services and creating a network of professionals, researchers, and specialists in standardization are the goals of the HSbooster.eu Training Academy. On the project website, all materials produced during the HSBooster.eu implementation are freely accessible—the opening of the HSbooster Training Academy services last year is developing the HSbooster.eu **website Standardisation Training Academy, Training Material, Serious Smiley Game and Training Academy Session: Introduction to Standardisation.**

Table 7 – Summary of Training Academy KPIs

Description	M30 KPI	M24 Status
Training – people trained	1,500	153 participants at webinars 5226 page views of online training academy content On site trainings: 25
Training Academy Webinars	14 (6 of which dedicated to training)	7
Contributions teaching materials to Training academy	25	15
Workshops	3	1

3.1 Contribution EAG on the Training Academy

The EAG offered impartial, external guidance to enhance the Project's visibility on a global scale. It is crucial for HSbooster to maintain a focused approach in order to unlock synergies at the pan-European level and maximize the impact of the allocated resources.

Contribution of EAG members to review of training materials: Invitations were sent out to all of the EAG members on the 15th of January, as per the plan. The review is due by the 15th of February, and a report on the review will be submitted by the end of February.

Contribution of EAG members to training sessions: Additionally, continuous conversations are taking place with members of the EAG who took part in the HSbooster trainings:

- Maitane Olabarria from SBS participated as a trainer at the third training session, **“Standards users and use of standards”**.
- Knut Blind (to be released on February, 1st) will participate in joint HSbooster.eu & StandICT2026 training session: **When is the right time for standardisation in research projects?**

3.2 Impact of the Training Academy

Task 5.1 focuses on the creation and operation of the HSbooster.eu Training Academy, with a methodology developed and training material structure defined in M3. The methodology

The HSbooster.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) - under grant agreement no 101058391.

was presented in a webinar on September 27th, 2022, providing valuable advice for task development.

The HSBooster.eu training academy published the beta version on April 21st, 2023. Up to now **24** written materials are published, with more than **600** pages. Up to now the training material has been viewed **5226** times.

3.2.1 Impact of the Training Academy on Experts.

Engaging in standards-making activities can facilitate the establishment of communities and connections with others who are actively involved in your field or similar domains. This engagement can contribute to the expansion of your professional networks. KPI5.3: Up to now, we have **15** contributions of experts on training academy (**the KPI is 25 teaching contributions**):

1. Irene Kamara, Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology, and Society, The Netherlands
2. Kai Jacobs, RWTH Aachen University, Germany
3. Maryam Pourrahim, PhD candidate at Tilburg Law and Economics Center (TIELC), the Netherlands, & Faculty of law of the University of Fribourg, Switzerland
4. Gemma Castejón, Martín Soriano Disla, CETENMA, Spain
5. Yoko Ikeda, Research Institute for Economy, Trade and Industry (RIETI), Michiko Iizuka, National Graduate Research Institute for Policy Studies (GRIPS), Japan
6. Barry P. Cox, NSAI video, Ireland
7. Chiara Giovannini, ANEC
8. Maitane Olabarria, SBS.
9. Ashok Ganesh, CEN-CENELEC
10. David Boswarthick, ETSI
11. Dr Sawet Malik, University Galway
12. Elsa Batista, IPQ TBR
13. Knut Blind, TU Berlin
14. Christian Goroncy, DIN
15. Nikolaj Zangenberg, Danish Technological Institute,

3.2.2 Impact of the Training Academy on SDOs.

Collaborations with SDOs have been present since the start of the HSbooster.eu Training Academy. The methodology of the training academy was presented at Webinar Building the HSbooster.eu Standardisation Training Academy - Experiences and lessons learned from Standardisation Training in Europe (27th September 2022) in which representatives of **6** SDOs (CEN-CENELEC, ETSI, UNE, UNI, DIN and DS) was participated as panelists and provided valuable advices for the start. The webinar had **90** participants, was downloaded for **75** times and viewed **245** times.

The HSbooster.eu Training Series Standardisation in Practice aims to make European NSBs' activities closer to researchers. Through various topics relevant to researchers' activities, the training sessions of this series intend to introduce the work of national standardisation bodies

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and provide some answers on how the NSBs can support research projects. Representatives of SDOs participated as trainers at two training sessions during reporting period:

- **Training Session 2: European Standardisation System (15 June 2023):** This training session aimed to improve the understanding of standards through guidance and training, provide more information on the benefits of the European Standardisation System, and bring the work of European Standardisation Organisations closer to researchers. Trainers at this training session were Ashok Ganesh, CEN-CENELEC and David Boswarthick, ETSI. The webinar had **60** participants, was downloaded for **79** times and viewed **306** times.
- **Training Session 5: Standardisation in practice: Roles of NSBs and identifying gaps in the current standards (21 Dec 2023):** This training session aimed to explain the role of the NSBs based on the case of the national standardisation body of Ireland – NSAI. The webinar had **13** participants, was downloaded for **25** times and viewed **113** times.

3.2.3 Impact of the Training Academy on Services. (M5.3)

With Development Training Academic (TA), we gained practical experience with services and experts. Experts' and projects' contributions to the TA could be significantly enhanced. The educational aspect of standardisation is attended to through the provision of an accessible training center and an effective mechanism for the development of standardisation competencies and skills.

3.2.4 Impact of the Accessed to Material

The Academy provides a variety of educational resources, developed by top researchers and trainers, covering various domains like ICT, health, safety, quality management, energy, environmental management, and food safety, accessible at beginner, intermediate, and advanced levels. The HSBooster.eu training academy published the **beta** version on **April 21st, 2023**. Up to now **24** written materials are published, with more than **600** pages. Up to now the written training material has been viewed **5226** times.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy Session 1: Introduction to Standardisation (4 May 2023):

This training session aimed to bring standardisation closer to those without prior knowledge of standardisation. By using interactive approaches, the training was focused on providing answers to the following questions: why do researchers need standards and standardisation; what is standardisation, and what are standards; and who develops standards? The training session had **60** participants, was downloaded for **45** times and viewed **233** times.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy Session 2: European Standardisation System (15 June 2023): This training session aimed to explain the basics of the European Standardisation System and bring the work of European Standardisation Organisations closer to researchers. The training session had **60** participants, was downloaded for **79** times and viewed **306** times.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy Session 3: Standards Users and Use of Standards (20 June 2023): Standards are developed to be used. A successful standard is a standard that is accepted in the market. Understanding standards users might be a changing point in

understanding the needs for one standard. There are plenty of reasons why the voice of direct and indirect standards users is vital in standardisation development. This training session aimed to raise awareness of standards users and bring the work of Small Business Standards (SBS) and the European Association for the Coordination of Consumer Representation in Standardisation (ANEC) closer to researchers. The training session had **47** participants, was downloaded 61 times and viewed **242** times.

HSbooster.eu Training Academy Session 4: Conformity Assessment Schemes and Systems: This training session aimed to bring conformity assessment schemes and systems closer to researchers. The training session had 64 participants, was downloaded for **17** times and viewed **53** times.

HSbooster.eu Training Session 5: Standardisation in practice: Roles of NSBs and identifying gaps in the current standards (21 Dec 2023): This training session aimed to explain the role of the NSBs based on the case of the national standardisation body of Ireland – NSAI. The webinar had **13** participants, was downloaded for **25** times and viewed **113** times.

HSbooster.eu Gaming Session 1: Serious Smiling Game: The Serious Smiling Game is a role-playing game that simulates the discussion in an ad hoc working group within the imaginary organisation for standardisation. This game aims to develop soft skills needed in standardisation processes, focusing on argumentation skills, strategic positioning, building compromise and common understanding. This serious game is developed by HSbooster.eu and House of Knowledge. It can be played onsite and online. The Serious Smiling Game online version is played in teams of five members each. Each team has its own facilitator, trained to support the players when necessary. Twenty players can participate in one term. Game session was held on the 23rd. June 2023. and the game is played with **10** participants.

Playing HSbooster.eu Serious Smiling Game: On the first day of the **EURAS** conference, 28th June in Aachen, Germany at RWTH Aachen University **25** conference participants from Germany, the Netherlands, Lithuania, Sweden, Switzerland, the U.S., Italy, Finland, Canada, and India played the Serious Smiley Game. Experiences are positive, and we receive valuable feedback from experienced educators and researchers in standardisation.

Figura 2 – Playing HSbooster.eu Serious Smiling Game on conference

The Serious Smiley Game, combines education, information, and entertainment, addressing real-world issues and enhancing skill development. It hones key soft skills for effective standardisation processes, including argumentation, strategic positioning, compromise building, and mutual understanding.

Table 8 – The impact the HSbooster.eu Training Academy on Series of Webinar

Date	Series	Zenodo Uploads	Views	Download	Videos	Views
27 Sep 2022	Introductory Webinar	Building the HSbooster.eu Standardisation Training Academy	90	75	Generic webinar	245
4 May 2023	Introduction to Standardisation	HSbooster.eu Training Academy Session 1: Introduction to Standardisation	60	45	TA1	233
15 Jun 2023	Introduction to Standardisation	HSbooster.eu Training Session 2: European Standardisation System	60	79	TA2	306
23 Jun 2023	Gaming Session	HSbooster.eu Gaming Session 1: Serious Smiling Game	47	27	TA3	218
20 Jun 2023	Introduction to Standardisation	Training Academy Session 3: Standards Users and Use of Standards	47	61	GA1	242
7 Dec 2023	Introduction to standardisation	Training Session 4: Conformity Assessment Schemes and Systems	64	17	TA4	53
21 Dec 2023	Standardisation in Practice	Training Session 5: Roles of NSBs and identifying gaps in the current standards	13	25	TA5	113
		Total	381	329	Total	1410

3.2.5 Standardization in Academics Conferences and webinars:

To date (M22), the HSbooster.eu Training Academy has Developed a framework for a series of training webinars focusing on standardization and presentations /webinars/conferences directed towards the European NSBs, ISO/IEC community, and EC officers.

STS Conference Graz 2023: The 21st Annual STS Conference Graz 2023, Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies is the joint Annual Conference of the Science Technology and Society Unit of the Institute of Interactive Systems and Data Science of Graz University of Technology, the Inter-University Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture (IFZ) and the Institute for Advanced Studies of Science, Technology, and Society (IAS-STs).

The University of Belgrade, an esteemed HSbooster.eu partner, has submitted an abstract and a paper titled:

- Mijatović, I., Kićanović, A., & Tošić, B. (2023). Ethics Assessment of R&D Supported by Standardisation. Book of Abstracts of the 21st Annual STS Conference Graz 2023 titled "Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies", Session B.1.

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"(Responsible) Standardization for (the Digital) Society", pp. 50-51. Graz University of Technology. ISBN 978-3-85125-955-1. [M34].

- Mijatović, I., Kićanović, A., & Tošić, B. (2023). Ethics Assessment of R&D Supported by Standardisation. Proceedings of the 21st Annual STS Conference Graz 2023 titled "Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies", Session B.1. "(Responsible) Standardization for (the Digital) Society", pp. tba. Graz University of Technology. ISBN tba. [M33].

This Conference samples several thematic fields as a guideline to address contemporary challenges of the interplay between science, technology, and society, among them Gender, Science and Technology, and Open Science: Rethinking the Science and Society Relationship. **EURAS 2023 Conference:** The 27th EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference and 12th International Conference on Standardisation and Innovation in Informative Technology (SIIT) "Responsible Standardisation for Smart Systems" was held from 28th to 30th June in Aachen, Germany. RWTH Aachen University hosted the conferences. At the conference panel on education about standardisation, held on 30 June from 16:30 to 18:00 CEST, Ivana Mijatovic presented information on the progress of the HSbooster.eu Training Academy. The other panelists were:

- Knut Blind, TU Berlin & FhG ISI, StandICT 2026
- Anna Gallet, ISO
- Amelie Leipprand, DIN
- Justina Bieliauskaite, DSME.

Figura 3 – Playing HSbooster.eu Serious Smiling Game with other panelists

The Training Academy also emphasises collaborative learning, fostering an environment where professionals can exchange ideas, share best practices, and build a network of like-minded individuals, further enhancing the learning experience.

The 2nd International Danube Cup Conference on Entrepreneurial Education: was held from 24th to 25th November at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Organisational Sciences. The conference's organiser is the Faculty of Organisational Sciences in cooperation with Corvinus University from Budapest. The Danube Cup is an international network of universities along the Danube River aiming to improve entrepreneurship education and support the launch of student startups in the region. The first conference was held in Budapest and organised by the Corvinus University of Budapest and the Budapest University of Technology and Economics.

The University of Belgrade, the HSbooster.eu partner, has submitted an abstract title:

- Mijatović, I., & Tošić, B. (2023). Bringing Standardisation Closer to Entrepreneurial Researchers. Book of Abstracts of the 2nd International Danube Cup Conference on Entrepreneurship Education (IDC2 E2 2023) titled "Entrepreneurship and Startup Education for Students", pp. 50-51. University of Belgrade – Faculty of Organizational Sciences. ISBN 978-3-85125-955-1. [M34].

Figura 4 – Paper Presentation at 2nd International Danube Cup Conference

AI Master Class 2023: The AI Master Class 2023, "Regulation of Artificial Intelligence: Legal and Ethical Challenges," was held on December 7 and 8, 2023, at the Science and Technology Park Novi Sad, Serbia. At the panel on the role of standards in regulating artificial intelligence, held on December 8 from 10:45 to 11:15 CEST, Ivana Mijatovic presented information about the HSbooster.eu. The other panelists were Oliver McCoy, IREX, Prof. Dr Tihomir Katulić, and Dr Niels ten Oever.

Figura 5 – Workshop on the European Partnership on Future Metrology

Webinar "Standards Academies: Towards the future of education on standardisation": This webinar aimed to address the increasing need for standardisation education and knowledge in Higher Education Institutes' curricula and its impact on economic growth, the "European Green Deal," the "New Industrial Strategy for Europe," and the Sustainable Development Goals. The EU-funded projects StandICT.eu and HSbooster.eu are working to close this gap on different levels, strategically relevant for European society and EU global leadership. HSbooster.eu has launched the HSbooster.eu Training Academy, in response to the Code of Practice on Standardisation, provides an efficient mechanism and accessible hub for training knowledge, expertise, and skills in the field of standardisation.

Webinar Women in ICT Standards, a focus on Gender Gap in ICT Standardisation and Standards: The link between technology and gender equality is growing stronger every year. It is reflected in Sustainable Development Goal 5 on gender equality and the empowerment of women, which includes a specific target on how to leverage technology and ICT assets to achieve women's empowerment fully. However, despite progress in this area, there is still a significant gender gap in ICT Standardisation, which affects diversity, equity, and inclusion in the field.

From Best Practice to Real Practice - Addressing standardisation priorities for R&I projects: STAND4EU and HSBooster.eu Joint Webinar: "From Best Practice to Real Practice - Addressing Standardisation Priorities for R&I projects" took place on Tuesday 12 December, from 10.30 to 12.00 CET online via Zoom. This webinar presents the best practices in standardisation, as highlighted by STAND4EU's trend workshops, and the experience of HSBooster.eu when providing services to address standardisation in research projects. A panel discussion with research projects and experts has discussed the findings and best practices identified. This panel discussion has allowed the audience to provide feedback on the difficulties faced and the best practices identified by both projects. The webinar will include an introduction by DG Research and Innovation on the code of practice on standardisation for researchers and relevant activities of the Commission in this area.

STAND4EU and HSbooster.eu are two projects under the Horizon Europe Programme that aim to strengthen the links between research, innovation and standardisation. STAND4EU seeks to identify the obstacles and potential remedies to address these obstacles and to develop communication platforms between the different actors. HSbooster.eu provides expert services to help Horizon Europe, Digital Europe Programme and H2020 projects to increase and valorise project results by contributing to standardisation in Europe and beyond.

4 The Impact of HSbooster.eu on Project Standardization Engagement

The primary goal of the HSbooster.eu Service was to demonstrate, through the use of concrete data and evidence, the advantages and significance of experts in facilitating and advancing projects towards achieving standards and standardization as project outcomes. Additionally, the service aimed to actively collaborate with relevant standards bodies, providing support and contributing to the development of their work.

4.1 Impact of the EPE and EAG on the projects

The methodology was designed to address premium service trackers using several research methods, including project questions, external pool of experts (EPE) consultancy and activity, building standards catalogue activity and working on it, access to the market, reviewed by EAG members, and a significant body of evidence was therefore collated for analysis. See block diagram below:

Figura 6 – Methodology of Impact of HSbooster.eu on Projects Standardization Engagement

Step 1: Project Questions and its Standardisation Objectives:

The projects below provided a short description of standardisation objectives when they applied in the application form; we can highlight projects looking for support for general knowledge or working in specific standards catalogue through the Premium service.

More details of the following project questions are available in Annex 1.

Step 2: EPE Consultancy and Activity Provided.

One of the significant impacts and benefits of HSbooster.eu lies in creating a community of experts, the EPE. Through its rigorous selection process, HSbooster.eu has established a diverse and knowledgeable pool of experts in its first year of activities.

The matchmaking service provided by HSbooster.eu identifies the best experts to support standardisation work programs for the participants. At the same time, the education/training material gives them the necessary background information to facilitate their engagement in standardisation.

We concentrate on showcasing a few instances of work being done on the projects that apply to the HSBooster.eu premium service. The EPE reports shown below demonstrate the advancements and results made possible by the advice and assistance of HSBooster.eu specialists.

More details of the following Consultancy and Activity Provided are available in Annex 2.

Step 3: Review and Analysis of Experts Reports by EAG Members.

The EAG provides independent, expert and external advice to the HSBooster.eu project. The group is compiled of individuals from a number of standards domains that are in a position to not just advise but also in the case of this impact review and capture important dates that the expert from the EPE has noted. The objective of this report is to disseminate the content and deliver expert insights from the data with an emphasis on Standards Catalogue, TCs & TWGs that were mentioned in the consultation.

More details of the following Step 3: Review and Analysis of Experts Reports by EAG Members are available in Annex 3.

4.2 EAG member insights and recommendations

We have received a total of thirty-five completed reports for Phase 1 from a variety of projects and fields.

1. Two members of the EAG are assigned to review each report and offer their expert feedback.
2. Each EAG member will review a total of seven reports during the initial phase of reviewing Expert / Project reports.
3. We received a total of 31 recommendations from the 35 reports that have been reviewed by EAG.
4. The table below shows the insights and recommendations of EAG members initially assigned to partners for evaluation and dissemination to the projects.

Table 9 – EAG member insights and recommendations

No	EAG Member	Project	EAG member insights and recommendations
1	Gavin Jones	EnerMan	To apply to the "StandICT Open Calls .
	Pamela Hussey	ECRAID-Base	
	Martin Chapman	CPSoSaware	
2	Maitane Olabarria	ROMSOC	1- Establish a liaison with some relevant TCs . 2- Access the standards mentioned some help accessing the texts could also be provided. 3- Work on the set of the new standards for the industry,
3	Maitane Olabarria	HELIOS	Recommendations on becoming a member of a mirror committee .
4	Sebastian Hallensleben	HERCCULES	1- Provide Better access to information on standardisation work in Europe and internationally. 2- Provide budgets in Horizon project funding to buy relevant standards , even beyond the HSBooster programme.
5	Speranta Stomff	CyberSEAS	Create a license agreement with national standards body to follow standards of interest, Buy/access to 1-3 key standards in project subject area.
6	Pamela Hussey	VALUECARE	1- as a next step identify 2 to 3 standards that can be of potential use and document lessons learned that can be shared as use cases of adoption, with the potential to be shared with the standardization working group. 2- The approach that the author used in the engagement process and the detail in the report was I think appropriate, there may be scope to use this as part of the training academy form for future report author engagement?
7	Pamela Hussey	PREMUROSA	This expert provides a dedicated training seminar for all the 13 PhD students in the premurosa project and follow up as needed. It would be worth creating a bank of resources from the experts' presentations perhaps for future use catalogued for easy access?
8	Pamela Hussey	Policy Cloud	Standardization, Smart Cities and Digital Twins. The chairs and contact persons who could be interested were named by the expert. The main constraint would be the lack of resources due to the end of the Policy Cloud project. Future networking may be possible to monitor the uptake of collaboration in advancing the project and associated processes.
9	Pernille Hagedorn	ECRAID-Base	To the end, the project wants to promote the COGITO results to at least 5 standardization bodies and to at least 4 standards.

EAG meeting with EPE: While reviewing the reports, HSbooster recommended a one-on-one meeting between the EAG and the EPE. Gavin Jones from BSI had an online meeting with Ilona Anna Cieslik, an expert on the project AI-PROFICIENT. During the meeting, they provided an overview of their expertise on standards and the project, in response to Gavin's inquiries about the service and the expert. She described her application process, her assignment based on her experience, and how she received the project from HSbooster. She also shared how she started working on the project and contributed her expertise in AI and transportation standardizations.

5 Standards Catalogue tracks all Standards documents impacted by HSbooster.eu

The main purpose of a Standards Catalogue is to lay out specific quality and safety standards that products, services, and processes must meet. Businesses may assure the consistency, safety, and high quality of their products and services by following recognized standards. Companies are required to adhere to specific quality and safety standards, which are enforced by regulatory agencies and governments through the usage of Standards Catalogues.

As part of the HSBooster.eu project, one of our key initiatives is to provide a comprehensive Standards Catalogue. The crucial information was contained within the reports prepared by the expert during their service. This would also help in shaping the standards that are relevant to our projects. Considering the wide range of emerging technologies, our input could be valuable to multiple committees.

Additionally, we need assistance identifying the committee where our efforts would have the most significant impact. In addition, it enables effective project planning, execution, and quality assurance by providing a concise and structured framework that outlines the pertinent standards and their alignment with the project's objectives.

However, we aim to actively engage with standardization organizations and understand how we can effectively influence the standardization process. Additionally, we are interested in learning how to propose new items to technical committees within these organizations.

This report provided an overview of the impact of the HSbooster.eu standards catalogue and presents the results of the practical guidance and support offered. It also emphasizes the proactive measures taken to engage with the most appropriate SDO or WG in order to guide the projects towards the most promising standardization pathways.

5.1 Analysis of the Standards Catalogue results

The aim of HSbooster.eu is to enhance the influence of European standardization. This is achieved by analyzing and addressing both the process of standardization and the resulting standards through the provision of support services (Premium Services). Additionally, HSbooster.eu acts as a facilitator project, offering practical guidance and assistance to selected research and innovation projects, helping them navigate the appropriate channels to contribute to sustainable development goals and the twin transition. This is accomplished through the recommendations by the expert to the project of standards, TC and working groups relevant to the projects requirements.

During the creation of the standards catalogue and reviewing how the project can measure the role and impact of standardisation in European projects, the following two distinct results emerged. Out of the total of **35 projects, 15 were undertaken in collaboration with a NSB and/or TC** with the objective of addressing and engaging with Standard and TC-related matters. See Figure 7.

More details of the following The Standards Catalogue table Provided are available in Annex 4.

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Standards Catalogue (TC and Standards)

Figura 7 – Standard and TC Experts Recommended

Out of the total of 35 projects, 20 of them were focused on standardisation strategy and involve communication and coordination with the relevant TCs, SCs, and WGs. Experts recommended buying or adopting standards or TC with the central offices of SDOs such as ISO, IEC, IEEE, CEN, CENELEC, or any other relevant organizations for the projects (see Figure 8).

Figure 8 shows the total number of "Experts Recommended" items in each category based on the TC standards. Also, the graph shows that the strong area of the recommendation is 21.2% of the total recommended "ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27" standard "Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection." This is the higher recommended standard for the projects KITT4SME and HELIOS. Other standards, such as ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41-Internet of Things and Digital Twin and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42-Artificial Intelligence, also need to be used for projects like these.

The minimum standards or TC recommended by the experts are 1.5% of the total project recommendation. The ISO/TC 260 - ISO 30401:2018 standard "Knowledge management systems" is highly recommended for the KITT4SME project.

Figura 8 – Standard and TC Projects Collaboration

The European Standard (EN) in the table is defined as a "standard adopted by CEN and/or CENELEC and carrying with it an obligation of implementation as an identical national standard and withdrawal of conflicting national standards". See Figure 9.

Figura 9 – Technical Committee Recommended Engagement

The number of "Experts Recommended" items in each category for each project topic is shown in Figure 9. Furthermore, the graph shows that the strong area of the recommendation is 14.3% of all the "18" standards for "Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection for many projects (HELIOS, SENTINEL, and GLASS) with different standards." The second most-requested domain is cloud computing and distributed computing, with about 14

projects requesting 11.1% of all the recommendations for projects (NEBULOUS and KITT4SME).

Figure 10 illustrates the cumulative count of "Experts Recommended" according to the project's requirements for working with or adapting to the standards or technical committee (TC). The graph illustrates that several projects, namely NEBULOUS with 18 standards, TC with 17 occurrences, and ROMSOC with 11 occurrences, have significantly large numbers. Additionally, The study also showed how useful the suggestions were for getting the projects to work on or be a structured part of goals with standards or TC.

Figura 10 – Project Recommended Engaged with Standards

The HSBooster project has already begun to communicate the benefits of employing standardization efforts in research projects, and the work of all initiatives should undoubtedly be continued. To ensure that the project results can be used realistically and presented to the market, it is critical for a research project to know and be able to use the standards in its field of activity from the outset of implementation.

The fundamental objective for this work, as well as the primary contribution that it makes to the report, is to demonstrate how incorporating EPE into the projects could increase the likelihood that the project will adhere to the standard. As a result of looking at these results, it appears that: The majority of projects recommended beginning with standards; low numbers from diagrams such as IMPETUS show that the project needs to work only with one standard, and higher numbers, such as the NEBULOS project, indicate that the project needs to work with 18 different standards that cover a variety of domains.

HSBooster will continue with the development of the standards catalogue repeating the process of engaging the Expert Advisory Group to disseminate the content of the next 35 completed expert reports. This will broaden the content of the current catalogue and then the partners can make future recommendation for a possible HSBooster project.

6 Impact on Policy

The commission is intrigued by HSBooster.eu and how it has influenced the EC's decision to provide funding for a future booster and seek the micro areas for the upcoming recommendations report in February, which will have a direct impact on the EC's decision-making process.

HSbooster.eu, will present its findings and recommendations in a policy brief for policymakers and actors. If interest is high, events like Policy Workshops can be organized to exchange views.

1. The plan aims to promote European Standards Bodies (NSBs) Cen-CENELEC and ETSI, inspire similar actions among other NSBs, and hand over HSBooster.eu to the European Commission (EC) or new consortium. It also promotes EPE experts' database to the EC, involving promotional materials, written input, and presentations to European NSBs, ISO/IEC community, and EC officers.
2. HSbooster.eu supports EU R&I projects by providing support services, enabling them to use existing standards, revise them, or create new ones, enhancing market access and aligning with the European green agenda.
3. HSbooster.eu addresses EU-level policy needs, including the Scoping study for standardisation code of practice. It facilitates standardization, helping researchers and innovators bring their innovations closer to the market and disseminate technological advancements, contributing to standardization.
4. HSbooster.eu supports UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Union's economic resilience, promoting climate-neutral, resilient, and circular standards, aligning with the Union's ambitions.
5. HSbooster.eu supports European and global standardisation projects, helping the Union maintain its position as a global standard-setter and strengthening its strategic autonomy. It empowers researchers and innovators to leverage standards for seamless integration and compatibility in digital transformation across various industries.

Lastly, the project has been able to attend or be represented by the EC at a number of policy-related EC meetings where the booster's goals and progress have been discussed:

- Updated EU on budget situation and the budget allocated to WPs in financial terms: 23/01/2024.
 - Outlined the current progress of service-related activities in the 30-month HSBooster.eu project, specifically focusing on the WP2 Platform, digital processes and open calls, and WP3 Services and support.
- HSbooster.eu M18 Status Update 07/12/2023.
 - An overview of the project's structure, output, and different aspects of the design and delivery of the services.
- EU Update, Amendment and services 21/09/2023.

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- Discussed the points raised in the amendment and gave EC an update on the project.

The Training Academy

The Standards Academy will streamline training and ensure project results are communicated to key stakeholders through carefully selected reports, including policy briefs and standards impact reports. HSbooster.eu Training Academy promotes standards in research and technology development, enhancing expertise through training programs, cited in Commission Recommendation 2023/498 for training materials.

At this point in time (M22), the HSbooster.eu Training Academy has developed a framework for a series of training webinars that will concentrate on standardization and presentations, webinars, and conferences that will be aimed at European National Standards Boards, the ISO/IEC community, and European Commission officers.

Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and Research Offices

We have identified relevant contacts and channels to approach TTOs and Research Offices, established effective communication with selected organisations, and crafted targeted key messages. HSbooster.eu actively engages with TTOs and Research Offices through specific communication channels. This outreach will showcase the advantages and worth of HSbooster.eu's assistance in standardisation activities for research projects, underscoring how it can enhance the efforts of TTOs and Research Offices:

- The key messages to communicate: Highlighting the shared goals between HSbooster and TTOs and Research Offices, such as accelerating and maximizing research impact, promoting innovation, and facilitating successful collaborations between academia and industry.
- Assistance is provided to tackle challenges in standardisation, such as guidance through standardisation processes and filling knowledge gaps in specific areas.
- Success stories: showcasing examples of how HSbooster has effectively supported R&I projects.

HSbooster.eu has been in dialogue with <https://www.astp4kt.eu/>, an umbrella organization for TTOs, and discussed the possibility of offering workshops and training sessions to their members. ASP4KT are also interested in utilizing the HSbooster.eu training material and dialogue with them will continue in 2024. This will be an ongoing objective of the project.

- Collaborative Workshops/Webinars
- Networking Opportunities: Foster connections between Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), research offices and HSbooster.eu.
- Enhance collaboration with the European IP Helpdesk to utilize their specialized knowledge in intellectual property rights and standardization.
- Use of HSbooster training academy and other tools by TTOs and Research Offices

Additionally, HSbooster.eu has been in dialogue with a selected group of specific offices. This includes the office at the University of Southern Denmark, Region H Denmark, and the TTOs at the University of Bologna and the University of Belgrade. This has resulted in further

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requests e.g. from Region **H** on specific standards and norms to be used by their projects and in their project proposals.

HSbooster.eu policy and sustainability

The consortium will closely monitor events and actively engage in policy and sustainability efforts, showcasing HSbooster.eu at various international SDO events.

The HSBooster consortium decided with the support of the EAG to create an open space on its website to facilitate multidirectional engagement between the ecosystem (e.g., Policy makers, Standardisation Bodies, Experts and Projects). This open space may facilitate the establishment and promotion of synergies to create a closer interaction between all interested stakeholders in better communicating, either stimulating the enrichment of existing standards or the creation of new standards and, also very important, to better understand the importance of standards when developing new products or services as a competitive asset for European industry and a more relevant role of Research and Innovation players assume.

In the future we estimate to incorporate over 20 projects in this embryonic ecosystem but to foster a rapid increase of participants to foster a closer communication between policy makers, standardisation bodies and experts with Projects representants, especially SMEs. SDO, will be invited as well as Policy Makers and, of course, projects and experts to be part of this space where interaction can progress beyond HS Booster project duration.

All of the profiles mentioned before could be structured by research area, technology or any criteria of interest that may contribute to a better understanding, adoption and promotion of standardisation.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Impact Report presented by the consortium has demonstrated at this stage of the project the work that was completed in year 1 has proven impactful in year 2. The solid foundation that was created and demonstrated via webinars, training academy, premium services, and continuous connection with both the projects and the experts in supporting them.

The final circle of support and impact for the original projects will be delivered via a survey in the final months of the project. As we continue to engage with new projects and experts, the survey will return to the initial projects, finding out if the support they received from the experts **worked and where HSbooster can support them from here**.

The delivery of V1 of a Standards Catalog that monitors the standards recommended by a HSbooster.eu service would greatly assist in identifying the standards committees where our contribution to standards would be most advantageous. This will be further expanded in the final months of the project via the EAG engagement.

D4.3 Intermediate Standards Impact Report deliverables provide a pragmatic and extensive summary of the HSBooster.eu impact achieved. The report highlights noteworthy results and meaningful figures, stakeholders addressed, the strategy deployed to enhance the promotion and correlated dissemination, and key-takeaways for the audience from the training session.

Annex 1 – HSbooster.eu Step 1: Project Questions and its Standardisation Objectives:

Project Name: FLEXnCONFU

Why the project is applying for a Standardisation Booster service:

We aim at understanding the standardization framework related to P2H and P2A solutions. In case needed we consider the opportunity to share our developments and point of view to specific workgroups. Also, specify a certification strategy.

The Task has been structured according to the following steps:

1) SETTING THE GROUND

- Analysis of the “P2H and P2A solutions and related background” to extract relevant information on regulatory framework and on **standardization and certification aspects**.

Starting from that, consolidate a list of key concepts and keywords related to the Topics as a starting point for a structured standards search.

2) STANDARD SCENARIO ANALYSIS

- Based on identified topics, extensive search of relevant standards
- Through the standards, the relevant technical bodies (technical committees TC, subcommittees SC and working groups WG) will be identified as well as other fields for the search, such as the International Classification of Standards (ICS)

3) Standards and standardization bodies clustering and mapping

The activity will have two different objectives: to identify the main bodies to enter in contact with to disseminate project results and to identify the responsible working groups to follow standards evolution (if possible).

4) Cross-linking of identified standards and Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

- Match the identified list of standards and standardization bodies with FLEXnCONFU project results.
- Propose actions for each of the **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)** regarding standardization and certification actual status and future perspectives.

Project Name: OASEES

Why the project is applying for a Standardisation Booster service:

We need support to identify the application of standard and shared compatible formats and protocols for gathering and processing data from different sources in a coherent and interoperable manner across sectors and vertical markets should be encouraged through the rolling plan for ICT standardisation and (as regards public services) a strengthened European Interoperability Framework.

The project has several potential outcomes that could contribute to standards, however, there is a lack of guidance to identify the proper standardization bodies as well as the procedure to contribute.

Project Name: PestNu

Why the project is applying for a Standardisation Booster service:

We think the booster service would be most beneficial in helping identify standards committees where our input into standards would be most beneficial/ help with influencing standards relevant to the project. As the technologies developed are quite different from each other it means that there could be a number of different committees that our input could be useful in, but it's identified where that effort would most likely be realised that we would like help with.

Which Technical Committee(s), Sub-committee(s) or Working Group(s) the project would like to contribute

ISO/TC 307 & CEN-CLC/JTC 19 Blockchain, Distributed Ledger Technologies

ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC 42 & CEN-CLC/JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection

CEN/CLC/JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection

These are ones we've identified so far, only based on the profile of the partner that is leading the standards task already being involved in these committees already. Would be open to being involved in ISO/TC 282/SC 1/WG1 – Treated wastewater use for irrigation projects or ISO/TC 34/SC 17 Food products - Management systems for food safety for example.

Annex 2 – Step 2: EPE Consultancy and Activity Provided.

EPE Report	
Expert: Dr. Muslim Elkotob	Topic: Sustainable digitalisation.
Project: ROMSOC	Subtopic: Data quality and Artificial Intelligence.

2) Description of first meetings

Abstract/Executive Summary

Subproject ESR2 of the European ROMSOC project deals with: Mathematical modeling and numerical simulation of coupled thermos-acoustic multi-layer systems for enabling particle velocity measurements in the presence of airflow.

The core objectives of this short consulting service include:

- To briefly analyze the standardization potential and perspectives of the work done in ESR2 on developing a digital twin of an acoustic device.
- To recommend a set of further potentially relevant standards to look at (in the areas of Digital Twins and Device Simulation).
- To provide a high-level description of important steps for successfully standardizing work in the Digital Twins area.

This is all highlighted further and in more detail in this report.

Note/Disclaimer: none of the references, products, standards mentioned in this document have a commercial or business relationship with me; I have no stake in any of the mentioned references and assets. Some of them I know from experience and may recommend checking them for relevance or technical merit.

Part 2: Important Aspects/Steps for Producing a Successful Standard in the Digital Twins Area

Alignment of Industrial Modelling/Prototyping and Standardization (e.g. ISO)

Here, it is important to follow a structured approach, with every major step of the modeling aligning to existing industry standards. This helps the overall adoption of the developed model into the standards of an SDO (as ISO, ETSI, ITU ..) to be a smooth and quicker process when some of its building blocks are in-line with commonly established norms.

In case ROMSOC ESR2, a prototype has already been developed together with the Dutch manufacturer Microflown Technologies, it is still recommended to check the various design steps and workflows/interfaces and see to which industry standards they are closest to. In the previous section of this document, a selected set of relevant standards in the area of Digital Twins in connection with industrial modelling and other use cases is presented.

A common example is using *Rapid Prototyping (RP) with ISO* as a major step towards standardizing an industrial model or device prototype. This goes in a complementary fashion with ISO as the former (RP) allows building in new features and functionalities with a desired range of parameters and the latter provides a diversion-safe frame for staying within the frame.

Some important recommendations to follow if doing Rapid Prototyping (or Re-Prototyping):

Modelling should go through relevant production phases to comply with standards.

Being aware of and highlighting the model design purposes is important, just as aligning those to the ISO instructions per design-purpose (type).

Digital Twin model product feature control to be run regularly (e.g. for compliance with SDO (e.g. ISO)) norms.

Developers of a digital twin for an industrial model/device can use RP to implement that model while being creative with the new concepts and still aligning to the norms. ISO guidelines (or standards guidelines in general) help check the design/model for conformity and regulatory compliance.

Some examples of rapid prototyping (RP) aligned to standards (such as ISO) include:

<https://jp-murphy.com/blog/iso-and-rapid-prototyping/>

<https://www.gtvinc.com/rapid-prototype-supplier-iso-certified/>

Selective Standardization of Parts of the Model

Picking specific aspects of the model, related to the algorithmic (methodology) or design (structural part) and mapping them to well-established standards as well as standardizing them with respect to the new part is a pragmatic approach. Candidate aspects for such activities include, but are not limited to:

Algorithms used for resolving the acoustic scattering problem.

Models for representing a 3D parametrized field for e.g. fluid-PML à working towards a blueprint or reference model for reuse by fellow experts and standards people in the industry.

Algorithms for acoustic oscillations and their representation and modelling based on certain environments.

Either the method used for representing the parametrized environment (geometry building and meshing), or the set of data and their respective structure as a reference model for future use can be standardized and put to use to the benefit of fellow industry experts.

Establishing any kind of blueprint, whether it is a reference model for grouping modelling data and parameters, or a skeleton for a set of use-cases, or a framing methodology to follow, has strong standardization potential and the ability to reach a wider audience of fellow experts, researchers, and industry professionals.

3.1) Standardisation readiness

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An evaluation of Standardisation Readiness Level of the project, An indication of the starting point in terms of standardisation and use of standards for the project.

3.2) Standards and standardisation mapping landscape

information on the standardisation landscape, relevant standards for the project, information on Technical Committees relevant for the project, Working Groups relevant for the project.

3.3) Access to standards

Use standards for new R&D proposals, Use of standards to check current market conditions or regulations, Buy/access to 1-3 key standards in project subject area.

3.4) Standardisation strategy and engagement

Become a member in 2 or more mirror committees of key interest to the research project, Participate in expert meeting with (national) WG experts on specific standard content e.g. in a mirror committee, Have an orientation/introductory meeting with central offices of SDOs (for instance ISO, IEC, IEEE, CEN, CENELEC or others)

3.5) Standards deliverables

Initiate /submit proposals for a new work item proposal (PWI/NWIP/NW) through the national standards bodies/national committees, Submit proposals for new work item in already existing TC/SC/WG, Participate in the development of already initiated standards deliverables at European or international level.

3.6) Training material

Standards and standardisation

3.6.1) Please specify any other training material suggested to the project in the box below

Part 1: Overview of Relevant Contemporary Digital Twins Standards

There are very few real standards for Digital Twins, as this is a relatively new area that needs maturing, including the standardization part. Furthermore, the planned activities in ROMSOC ESR2 for standardizing certain design models and their corresponding digital twins will be one of the early appearing standards outputs/outcomes for the wider community to build on, in the area of Reduced Order Modelling combined with Digital Twins.

Besides the mentioned ISO 12354-1:2017 standard already analyzed in the ROMSOC project, it is recommended to look into standards like:

ISO 23247-1:2021 Automation systems and integration — Digital twin framework for manufacturing; these standards set is structured as follows (for selective study/reading)

ISO 23247-1: General principles and requirements for developing digital twins in manufacturing.

ISO 23247-2: Reference architecture with functional views;

[ISO 23247-3](#): List of basic information attributes for the observable manufacturing elements;

ISO 23247-4: Technical requirements for information exchange between entities within the reference architecture.

ETSI GR ETSI GR CIM 017 V1.1.1 (2022-12) Context Information Management (CIM); Feasibility of NGSI-LD for Digital Twins

This standards document studies the application of Digital Twins to a complex environment with a Context Information Management (CIM) model.

The present document analyses the use of NGSI-LD information model and API for representation and handling of digital twins. It starts with a description of actual digital twin use cases, in several vertical domains. Then it provides an identification of relevant external technical initiatives. Finally, the present document provides concrete views on the definition of Digital Twins in an NGSI-LD ecosystem including identification of Digital Twin capabilities and life cycle stages. The final clauses analyse how, taking inspiration from actuation mechanisms, a service execution API could be defined to handle Digital Twin capabilities.

https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gr/CIM/001_099/017/01.01.01_60/gr_CIM017v010101p.pdf

3. ISO/TC 184/SC 4 Industrial data models, Digital Twin Advisory Group

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) covers industrial data in TC 184 SC 4. The standard for a Digital Twin Manufacturing Network is currently under development. For the Joint Technical Committee (JTC 1) that includes ISO and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), an established Joint Advisory Group (JAG) on Emerging Technology and Innovation (JETI) published their Technology Trend Report¹² and identified Digital Twin as one of four top emerging technologies out of fifteen. The report has led to formation of the Digital Twin Advisory Group (AG 11) who provide recommendations to JTC 1. <https://www.iso.org/committee/54158.html>

Some further useful references on Digital Twins include:

ETSI IEC TC 65: "Industrial-process measurement, control and automation"
https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:14089666729290:::FSP_ORG_ID:1250

ETSI TS 103 828: "SmartM2M; SAREF: Ontology Support for Urban Digital Twins and usage guidelines"
https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=63076

ISO/IEC AWI 30173: "Digital twin -- Concepts and terminology" <https://www.iso.org/standard/81442.html>

IEC Technology report: "City information modelling and urban digital twins" <https://www.iec.ch/basecamp/city-information-modelling-and-urban-digital-twins>

ISO. ISO 23247--2021 -- Automation system and integration -- Digital twin framework for manufacturing.
<https://www.iso.org/standard/75066.html>

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ISO. ISO/TR 24464--2020 -- Automation systems and integration -- Industrial data -- Visualization elements of digital twins. <https://www.iso.org/standard/78836.html>

IEEE. IEEE SA-P2806 -- System Architecture of Digital Representation for Physical Objects in Factory Environments. <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2806/7524/>

IEEE. IEEE SA-P2806.1 -- Standard for Connectivity Requirements of Digital Representation for Physical Objects in Factory Environments. <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2806.1/10370/>

ISO. ISO/IEC AWI 30172 -- Digital Twin -- Use cases. <https://www.iso.org/standard/81578.html>

ISO. ISO/IEC AWI 30173 -- Digital twin -- Concepts and terminology. <https://www.iso.org/standard/81442.html>

IEC. IEC 62832--2020 -- Industrial-process measurement, control and automation -- Digital factory framework. <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/65858>

ITU. ITU-T Y.3090 -- Digital twin network -- Requirements and architecture. <https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/recommendations/rec.aspx>

ITU. ITU-T Y.DT-interop -- Interoperability framework of digital twin systems in smart cities and communities. https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/workprog/wp_item.aspx

IRTF. Digital Twin Network: Concepts and Reference Architecture. <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-nmrg-network-digital-twin-arch/>

China Center for Information Industry Development (CCID) -- Digital twin white paper (2019). <https://www.ccidgroup.com/info/1096/21685.html>

IEEE. IEEE1451 -- IEEE Standard for a Smart Transducer Interface for Sensors and Actuators. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/4374241>

IEEE. IEEE 2888 -- Interfacing Cyber And Physical World Working Group. <https://sagroups.ieee.org/2888/>

3.6.2) Do you recommend that the service recipient completes any of the following (tick what appropriate)?

4) Final Recommendations

Part 3: High-level Recommendations for ROMSOC – ESR2 Project

There are two major possible paths that can be taken to place the results produced (designed, implemented) in terms of the digital twin of a high-precision acoustic device into standards:

1. Retrospective mapping of individual blocks of the design and workflow (and model in general) to specific standards (especially ISO standards) and using partially the standards listed and referenced in this report.
2. Following a second run approach: doing a Rapid Re-Prototyping (RP) of the developed model with sequential alignment to (ideally ISO, but potentially other e.g. ITU or ETSI) standards, ideally one reference standard (e.g. ISO 23247-1:2021).

The former approach has the advantage of saving the re-prototyping step but patching and fitting for matching the individual design and workflow steps to existing standards would be resource consuming on the flipside.

The latter approach can prove to be more advantageous or smooth to follow because it entails a holistic clean-slate approach to matching to existing standards as the development (or re-prototyping) progresses.

Further Recommended Reading(s)

The Digital Twin Book Chapter: Digital Twin Standards, Open Source, and Best Practices

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-21343-4_18

An Introduction to Digital Twins Standards <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3568113.3568119>

Checking Some Framework/Platform Type Commercial Solutions is recommended; an example is Twin-X from Tata Consultancy Services <https://www.tcs.com/what-we-do/industries/communications-media-information-services/solution/tcs-twinx-digital-twin-technology-solution>

Part 4: Outlook and Potential Next Steps

This report is a first step to set the frame for connecting the work done in ROMSOC ESR-2 to the world of standards and standardization. If the developed acoustic device model is successfully aligned to standards, and the new parts (either in individual blocks/steps or in the overall workflow/orchestration) are then set as new standards for the industry, this would be a pioneering piece of work and a trendsetter for further similar developments. As potential next steps, I would recommend analyzing the alternatives and then picking a “Plan A” path to proceed (from the suggestions in this report) and connecting to the SDO community. Then drawing a detailed workplan for running Plan A, potentially with consulting support if needed, could be a potential next step.

Closing Remarks: It is strongly encouraged to follow on this activity and to submerge the produced work and further similar efforts into the industry standards world. It has a lot of potential and can reach a wider community in the ecosystem when placed within an SDO Frame (as ISO, ETSI, ITU or others). Furthermore, the process intended here and the learnings acquired in the journey have guiding and pioneering potential for fellow developers and researchers out there.

EPE Report	
Expert: Ilona Anna Cieslik	Topic: Sustainable digitalisation.
Project: AI-PROFICIENT	Subtopic: Data quality and Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction on the project consortium and the key exploitable items. Identification of possible areas of standardisation in manufacturing (keywords):

1. Edge cases identification
2. Human Machine Interfaces (HMI) / Human machine factors (HMF)
3. Verification and validation methods / Digital Twins
4. Terminology / Taxonomies / Ontologies for manufacturing, predictive maintenance
5. Industrial sensors (calibration, etc.)
6. AI / Ethics / Safety / Cybersecurity

Ilona (expert) - presentation on the Standardisation as an introduction (1h)

Definitions and differences between standards and regulations.
 The landscape of SDO (global, European, and national standardisation bodies).
 Other types of standardisation institutes: - industry, consortia, open source driven, special initiatives for SME.
 Lesson learnt from R&D FP7, H2020 projects about how to approach Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) and how long the standardisation cycle could take (success stories vs. unsuccessful approaches).
 Recommendations and additional considerations about type of standards (terminology, process definition, testing/validation approaches, etc), TRL level, possible engagement with SDOs (proactive vs. observer), industrial/academic interest (commercial and non-commercial).

Open discussion and questions and answers, the definition of next steps (50 min)

Annex 3 – Step 3: Review and Analysis of Experts Reports by EAG Members.

EAG Submission information	
EAG Name: Speranta Stomff	
Report Author: MARGA MARTIN SANCHEZ	Project: NEBULOUS
Topic: Sustainable digitalisation	Sub-topics: Data quality and Artificial Intelligence

SERVICE REPORT DETAILS

In this report is there a reference or direct link to the "Code of Practice"?

No.

Is there a reference to the HSbooster.eu Training Academy, and if so, can you state the details?

No.

Has any of the following been listed in the report?

1. TWG- Technical Working Group.
2. Standards.

Please add more details about it.

Particular interest to ISO/IEC19941:2017-Cloud computing/Interoperability and portability and other complementary standards

Specific recommendation and information about:

- ISO / IEC JTC 1 / SC 38 "Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms",
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41: Internet of things and digital twin, groups,
- ETSI
- IEEE relevant WG in domain

How has the expert's guidance in the activity report addressed standards requests/priorities?

Recommendation for participation in already existing project of standards on European and international level

An extensive report with recommendations of the kind of SDOs and other standardization associations was provided to the consortium.

In the report, is there an opportunity or recommendation for a future standardisation booster project?

No.

Is there relevant information that we can recommend to the EU in regards to future standardisation?

No.

As an EAG member, what insights about the project and standardisation opportunities would be valuable for future standardisation initiatives?

An interesting project that could create a closer link between European standardization (deficient in this area) and European partners. Perhaps a continuation of the project with a greater emphasis on the standardization part would involve more European standardization in this direction.

INTERVIEW INFORMATION

Are you interested in arranging an interview?

{Empty}

Any new important information relevant to the HSbooster.eu project? (Negative or Positive)

No.

- Any new important information relevant to EU Commission.

Cloud computing standards are, in my opinion, a challenge for European standardization, due to the accelerated development of open standards in the field. At the CEN/CLC level there were initiatives related to open standards (e.g. Open Source Solution project, which was suspended after two years of quality due to lack of funds. The project was based on volunteering from NSBs and some large European companies), but nothing has been completed until now. A closer cooperation of CEN/CLC with OASIS, which is also active as a partner in various WGs and projects at European level, would be desirable.

EAG Submission information	
EAG Name: Pamela Hussey	
Report Author: Carlos Luis Parra Calderón	Project: ECRAID-Base
Topic: Sustainable digitalisation	Sub-topics: Access to and usage of data
SERVICE REPORT DETAILS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In this report is there a reference or direct link to the "Code of Practice"? No ● Is there a reference to the HSbooster.eu Training Academy, and if so, can you state the details? Yes the author recommends Participate in or watch recording of HSbooster training webinar ● Has any of the following been listed in the report? 3. Standards. ● Please add more details about it. Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization (CDASH) was mentioned and the in the project representatives were seeking guidance in creating a crossover between CDASH, which is widely used in regulatory clinical studies, and HL7 FHIR, as it is a standard in widespread use worldwide to represent clinical observational data. Specifically, the project team wished to obtain expertise in HL7 FHIR to perform the mapping between CDASH and HL7 FHIR. ● How has the expert's guidance in the activity report addressed standards requests/priorities? I think the expert provides good guidance to the project team over a series of three separate meetings. Specifically making recommendations for crosswalks between standards experts reports and evidence with relevant domain experts making the case for the necessary. clinical and context expertise to be synthesised in order to preserve critical information and to understand whether information from one standard is adequately mapped and documented in another. The expert also recommends clarifying and defining the scope of the service to optimise resource efficiency which is i think important. In addition to providing relevant evidence he also recommends future standards groups for the project team to access for better use of networking and adoption of standards at the lower end of the TRL adoption. ● In the report, is there an opportunity or recommendation for a future standardisation booster project? Possibly given the fact that the expert has signposed the project team to OHDSI forum to connect with the OMOP community and recommends the research team seek collaborations for OMOP mapping and engagement with the HL7 FHIR user groups. One idea i had was that at this level of engagement it may also be useful for the project team to consider reviewing ISO /TS 21564 Health Informatics — Terminology resource map quality measures (MapQual) section 4.4 building a map set. As this may be useful for the project team to use once the scoping of the project initiative has been determined as per experts guidance. ● Is there relevant information that we can recommend to the EU in regards to future standardisation? Yes I think the expert advocates the project team to apply for the open call of the StandICT.eu project. I would agree that due consideration should be given for this call to used as it is an excellent opportunity to seek funding since they intend to develop a CDISC and FHIR standards harmonization effort in the microbiology domain, which is of great interest for the impact and adoption of standards in the healthcare and biomedical research domain. ● As an EAG member, what insights about the project and standardisation opportunities would be valuable for future standardisation initiatives? I would recommend follow up and closer monitoring with this project and team particularly as they progress from early TRL (terminology and concept mapping) to later phases of TRL (interoperability and performance) to monitor progress and determine the impact of the 	

guidance provided. It would also be useful to look at the two way feedback loops between the team and SDO community over time.

INTERVIEW INFORMATION

- Are you interested in arranging an interview?
No
- Any new important information relevant to the HSbooster.eu project? (Negative or Positive)
It would be important to monitor progress between research teams and standard network groups to determine if there is better use of standards adoption and dissemination . Also perhaps to see if any spin off initiatives and networking of key individuals from both communities has grown from the initiative for faster adoption of the standards used.
- Any new important information relevant to the EU Commission.
I think this project could provide a good demonstrator of how HS Booster expert advice can advance standards. If recommendations are used by the project team, it is a good example of how R&I teams can tap directly into specialist SDO groups and networks to tackle EU priorities.

Annex 4 – The Standards Catalog Table

1	HELIOS	ISO 27701	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Specifies requirements and provides guidance for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving a PIMS in the form of an extension to ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 for privacy management within the context of the organization.	8/1/2019	No	-	CHF 187
2	HELIOS	Protocol 802.11	Standard	Link	Standards for New and Emerging Wi-Fi Use Cases	-	This standard and its subsequent amendments are the basis for Wi-Fi wireless networks and represent the world's most widely used wireless computer networking protocols.	6/19/1905	No	-	Free
3	ROMSOC	ISO 12354-1:2017	Standard	Link	Building acoustics	ISO/TC 43/SC 2	Specifies calculation models designed to estimate the airborne sound insulation between adjacent rooms in buildings, primarily using measured data which characterise direct or indirect flanking transmission by the participating building elements, and theoretically-derived methods of sound propagation in structural elements.	7/1/2017	Yes	Link	CHF 208
4	ROMSOC	ISO 23247	Standard	Link	Industrial data	ISO/TC 184/SC 4	Provides an overview and general principles of a digital twin framework for manufacturing including: terms and definitions; requirements of the digital twin framework for manufacturing.	10/1/2021	No	-	CHF 61
5	ROMSOC	ISO/TC184/SC 4	TC	Link	Industrial data	ISO/TC184/SC 4	Provides a overview of the whole ISO 15531 standard. It specifies its scope and provides a number of basic definitions on which the standard is built in accordance with the "General system theory", and the concepts defined in APICS dictionary.	3/1/2004	No	-	CHF 145
6	ROMSOC	ETSI IEC/TC 65	TC	Link	Industrial process measurement, control and automation	ETSI IEC/TC 65	To prepare international standards for systems and elements used for industrial process measurement, control and automation.	-	No	-	-
7	ROMSOC	ETSI TS 103 828	TC	Link	SmartMEM, SAREF Ontology Support for Urban Digital Twins and usage guidelines	ETSI TS 103 828	This deliverable will fill the priority gaps identified related to SAREF in DTF-SmartMEM-103827 and will include guidelines about how to use SAREF in the context of Urban Digital Twins and with Digital Twins	-	No	-	-
8	ROMSOC	ISO/IEC AW1 30173	Standard	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Establishes terminology for digital twin (DTs) and describes concepts in the field of digital twin, including the terms and definitions of digital twin, concepts of digital twin (e.g. digital twin system context, life-cycle process for digital twin, types of digital twin), functional view of digital twin, and digital twin stakeholders.	2023-11	No	-	CHF 145
9	ROMSOC	ISO/TR 24464-2020	Standard	Link	Industrial data	ISO/TC 184/SC 4	This document analyses visualization elements that are key components of the interface between the physical asset and the virtual (digital) replica of the physical asset).	2020-11	Yes	Link	CHF 124
10	ROMSOC	IEEE SA-P2806	Standard	Link	System Architecture of Digital Representation for Physical Objects in Factory Environments	CSAB - Standards Activities Board	This standard defines the system architecture of digital representation for physical objects in factory environments. The system architecture describes the objective, important components, required data resources and basic establishing procedure of digital representation in factory environments.	2019-03-21	No	-	-
11	ROMSOC	ISO/IEC AW1 30172	Standard	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Provides a collection of representative use cases of digital twin applications in a variety of domains, for example, smart manufacturing and smart cities.	2023-10	No	-	CHF 208
12	ROMSOC	IEC 62832-2020	Standard	Link	Industrial process measurement, control and automation	TC/SC 65	Defines the general principles of the Digital Factory framework (DF framework), which is a set of model elements (DF reference model) and rules for modelling production systems.	2020-10-26	No	-	CHF 220
13	ROMSOC	P1481-99	Standard	Link	Sensor Technology	EMST - TC9	This standard defines a method for data sharing, interoperability and security of messages over a network, where sensors, actuators and other devices can interoperate, regardless of underlying communication technology.	2020-09-24	No	-	-
14	HOUSEFUL	EN 15978	Standard	Link	Sustainability of construction works,	BS EN 15978:2011	Sustainability of construction works. Assessment of environmental performance of buildings. Calculation method is classified in these ICS categories: 91.040.99 Other buildings	1/31/2012	Yes	Link	317.40 EUR

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
15	HOUSEFUL	CEN/TC 350	Standard	Link	Sustainability of construction works.	CEN/TC 350	Development of horizontal standardized methods for the assessment of the sustainability aspects of new and existing construction works in the context of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and of the circular economy.	11/15/2013	No	-	\$146.37
16	HOUSEFUL	EN 15804	Standard	Link	Sustainability of construction works.	CEN/TC 350 - CEN/TC 350/WG 3	This European standard provides core product category rules (PCR) for Type III environmental declarations for any construction product and construction service.	1/1/2012	Yes	Link	\$374.04
17	ECRAID-Base	HL7 FHIR	Standard	Link	Health informatics	-	Defines a standardized model of the functions that may be present in PHR Systems. It is beyond the scope of the PHR system to control the use of PHR data.	3/22/2016	No	-	\$180.94
18	ECRAID-Base	ISO/TS 21564	Standard	Link	Health informatics	ISO/TC 215	Establishes measures which can be used to assess the quality and utility of a map between terminological resources in order to determine the types and levels of measure required for common use cases in healthcare.	6/1/2019	No	-	CHF124
19	BHELP	HL7 FHIR	Standard	Link	Health informatics	-	Standardized model of the functions that may be present in PHR Systems. It is beyond the scope of the PHR system to control the use (or intended use) of PHR data. On the contrary, it is within the scope of the PHR system to manage the authorization of an individual (or other application).	3/22/2016	No	-	\$180.94
20	GLASS	CEN/TC 224	TC	Link	Machine-Readable Cards, Related Device Interfaces and Operations	TC 224	Standards for strengthening the interoperability and security of personal identification and its related personal devices, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment.	-	No	-	\$39.03
21	GLASS	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC29/WG3	TC	Link	Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypertext information	JTC 1/SC29/WG3	Efficient coding of digital representations of images, audio and moving pictures	1991	No	-	-
22	GLASS	ISO/IEC 23000-23	Standard	Link	Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypertext information	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29	Under development	-	No	-	-
23	GLASS	ISO/IEC JTC 1	TC	Link	Information technology	JTC 1	Standardization in the field of information technology.	1987	No	-	-
24	GLASS	ISO/IEC SC 27	TC	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	JTC 1/SC 27	Development of standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both security and privacy aspects.	1989	No	-	-
25	GLASS	ISO/IEC SC 29	TC	Link	Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypertext information	SC 29	Efficient coding of digital representations of images, audio and moving pictures	6/13/1905	No	-	-
26	GLASS	ISO/TC 307	TC	Link	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies	TC 307	Standardisation of blockchain technologies and distributed ledger technologies.	7/8/1905	No	-	-
27	AFC4Hydro	ISOTC4	TC	Link	Rolling bearings	TC4	Standardization of all types and all sizes of bearing elements based on the principle of rolling motion, including the lubrication, their accessories, application and identification and standardization of spherical plain bearings, i.e. plain bearings with spherical contact surface.	4/30/1905	No	-	-
28	AFC4Hydro	IEC 62882	Standard	Link	Hydraulic machines - Francis turbine pressure fluctuation transposition	TC4	which is a Technical Specification, provides pressure fluctuation transposition methods for Francis turbines and pump-turbines operating as turbines.	9/18/2020	No	-	\$481.00
29	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC19941:2017	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Specifies cloud computing interoperability and portability types, the relationship and interactions between these two cross-cutting aspects of cloud computing and common terminology and concepts used to discuss interoperability and portability, particularly relating to cloud services.	2017-12	-	-	CHF187
30	NEBULOUS	ISO / IEC JTC 1 / SC 38	TC	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	JTC 1 / SC 38	Standardization in the areas of Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms including: foundational concepts and technologies, Operational issues, and Interactions among Cloud Computing systems and with other distributed systems.	2009	No	-	-
31	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	TC	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	JTC 1/SC 41	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 is being supported administratively by IEC. All information related to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 is available on the IEC web site Standardization in the area of IoT and related technologies.	2017	No	-	-

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
32	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 17788:2014	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Provides an overview of cloud computing along with a set of terms and definitions. It is a terminology foundation for cloud computing standards.	2014-10	Yes	Link	-
33	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 17789:2014	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Specifies the cloud computing reference architecture (CCRA). The reference architecture includes the cloud computing roles, cloud computing activities, and the cloud computing functional components and their relationships.	2014-10	No	-	-
34	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 27017:2015	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Gives guidelines for information security controls applicable to the provision and use of cloud services by providing: additional implementation guidance for relevant controls specified in ISO/IEC 27002; additional controls with implementation guidance that specifically relate to cloud services.	2015-12	No	-	CHF145
35	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 27018:2019	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Establishes commonly accepted control objectives, controls and guidelines for implementing measures to protect Personally Identifiable Information (PII) in line with the privacy principles in ISO/IEC 29100 for the public cloud computing environment.	2019-01	No	-	CHF124
36	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 19086-1:2019	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Seeks to establish a set of common cloud SLA building blocks (concepts, terms, definitions, contexts) that can be used to create cloud Service Level Agreements (SLAs).	2016-09	No	-	CHF145
37	NEBULOUS	ISO / IEC JTC 1 / SC 38	TC	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO / IEC JTC 1 / SC 38	Standardization in the areas of Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms including: Foundational concepts and technologies, Operational issues, and Interactions among Cloud Computing systems and with other distributed systems.	-	No	-	-
38	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC DIS 5140	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Concepts for multi-cloud and the use of multiple cloud services	Under development	Yes	Link	-
39	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC TS 5928	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Specifies a taxonomy related to digital platforms, by providing definitions and supporting information that disambiguates different uses of the term platform as it applies to digital services (such as cloud computing and other distributed computing systems).	2023-09	No	-	CHF145
40	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC AWI TS 7339	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Provides normative definitions of terms related to cloud computing technology platforms; a description of the concepts of platform capabilities type as it appears in various cloud service categories; a description of the specific cloud service category of platform as a service (PaaS).	Under development	No	-	-
41	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC AWI TR 10822-1	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Multi-cloud API Management, Multi-cloud service metering and billing, Multi-cloud environment	Under development	Yes	Link	-
42	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC AWI TS 10866	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Provides concepts related to the intersection of digital sovereignty, organizational autonomy, and digital platforms. It provides a framework enabling organizations	Under development	Yes	Link	-
43	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC FDIS 22123-2	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Specifies concepts used in the field of cloud computing. These concepts expand upon the cloud computing vocabulary defined in ISO/IEC 22123-1 and provide a foundation for other documents that are associated with cloud computing.	2023-09	No	-	-
44	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC FDIS 22123-3	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	This document specifies the cloud computing reference architecture (CCRA).	2023-09	Yes	Link	CHF187
45	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	TC	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization programme on the Internet of Things and Digital Twin, including their related technologies. Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, ISO and other entities developing Internet of Things and Digital Twin related applications.	-	No	-	-

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
46	NEBULOUS	ISO/IEC 21823	Standard	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Specifies the IoT interoperability from a syntactic point of view. In ISO/IEC 21823-1, Framework [2], five facets are described for IoT interoperability, i.e. transport, semantic, syntactic, behavioural and policy.	2022-03	No	-	CHF166
47	CIMPA	EN 15343	Standard	Link	Recycled Plastics	CEN/TC 249	This European Standard specifies the procedures needed for the traceability of recycled plastics. This gives the basis for the calculation procedure for the recycled content of a product.	12/5/2007	Yes	Link	\$46.35
48	CIMPA	DIN SPEC 91446	Standard	Link	Recycled plastics simplifies procurement and ensures quality.	-	Classification of recycled plastics by Data Quality Levels for use and digital trading facilitates your procurement process by bringing transparency about the materials being traded.	12/1/2021	Yes	Link	5.25 EUR
49	CIMPA	CEN/TC 249	TC	Link	PLASTICS	CEN/TC 249	Standardization of 1) terminology, 2) test methods, 3) specifications, classifications and designation systems, 4) environmental aspects, 5) joining systems and techniques, of plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products (thermoplastics, thermosets, degradable plastics, bio-based polymers, thermoplastic elastomers, composites, reinforcement products for plastics, recyclates).	-	-	-	-
50	CIMPA	CEN/TC 261	TC	Link	PACKAGING	CEN/TC 261	Responsible for the elaboration of standards dealing with terminology, dimensions, capacities, marking, test methods, performance requirements and environmental aspects in the field of packaging and unit loads. The field covers primary, secondary and transport packagings and unit loads, whatever the materials, shapes, contents or distribution system used.	-	-	-	-
51	REFLECT AFRICA	ISO/TC 282/SC 1	TC	Link	Treated wastewater reuse for irrigation	TC 282/SC 1	Standardization in the field of Treated wastewater (TWW) for irrigation requirements and processes involved in the development of health, environmentally viable and sustainable projects for the reuse of treated wastewater in all fields of irrigation.	2014	-	-	-
52	REFLECT AFRICA	ISO 16075-1:2020(en)	Standard	Link	Treated wastewater reuse for irrigation	ISO/TC 282/SC 1	This document contains guidelines for the development and the execution of projects intending to use treated wastewater (TWW) for irrigation and considers the parameters of climate and soil.	11/1/2020	No	-	CHF145
53	REFLECT AFRICA	ISO/TC 255	TC	Link	Biogas	ISO/TC 255	Standardization in the field of biogas produced by anaerobic digestion, gasification from biomass and power to gas from biomass sources.	-	No	-	-
54	REFLECT AFRICA	CEN/TC 383	TC	Link	SUSTAINABLY PRODUCED BIOMASS FOR ENERGY APPLICATIONS	CEN/TC 383	Standardization in the field of sustainably produced biomass for energy application, to provide agreements for producers to implement sustainable production, for certifiers to assess for conformity, and for authorities to set requirements for biomass.	-	No	-	-
55	PREMIUROSA	ISO 10993	Standard	Link	Biological and clinical evaluation of medical devices	ISO/TC 194	Specifies the general principles governing the biological evaluation of medical devices within a risk management process.	8/1/2018	Yes	Link	CHF166
56	PREMIUROSA	EN 12066-2 1998	Standard	Link	Non active surgical implants - Particular requirements for cardiac and vascular implants.	CEN/TC 285	Specific requirements for vascular prostheses, including cardiac valve conduits, of synthetic or biological origin intended to replace, to reconstruct, to bypass or to form shunts between segments of the cardio-vascular system in humans.	5/6/2009	Yes	Link	70 EUR
57	COGITO	ISO/IEC WD 30172	Standard	Link	Digital Twin - Use cases	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Under development	-	-	-	-
58	Merlin	MS84	Standard	Link	Recycled Plastics	CEN/TC 249	Plastics recycling and recycled plastics	-	Yes	Link	\$81.31
59	Merlin	CEN/TC 261	TC	Link	PACKAGING	CEN/TC 261	Responsible for the elaboration of standards dealing with terminology, dimensions, capacities, marking, test methods, performance requirements and environmental aspects in the field of packaging and unit loads. The field covers primary, secondary and transport packagings and unit loads, whatever the materials, shapes, contents or distribution system used.	-	-	-	-
60	Merlin	CEN/TC 249	TC	Link	PLASTICS	CEN/TC 249	Standardization of 1) terminology, 2) test methods, 3) specifications, classifications and designation systems, 4) environmental aspects, 5) joining systems and techniques, of plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products (thermoplastics, thermosets, degradable plastics, bio-	-	-	-	-
61	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 29100	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	ISO/IEC 29100:2011 provides a privacy framework which specifies a common privacy terminology.	12/1/2011	Yes	Link	CHF124

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
62	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27701	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides guidance for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving a Privacy Information Management System in the form of an extension to ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 for privacy management within the context of the organization.	8/1/2019	No	-	CHF187
63	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27001	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	World's best-known standard for information security management systems (ISMS). It defines requirements an ISMS must meet.	10/1/2022	No	-	CHF124
64	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 29190	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides organizations with high-level guidance about how to assess their capability to manage privacy-related processes.	8/1/2015	No	-	CHF92
65	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27035	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	It presents basic concepts, principles and process with key activities of information security incident management, which provide a structured approach to preparing for, detecting, reporting, assessing, and responding to incidents, and applying lessons learned.	2/1/2023	No	-	CHF145
66	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27552	Standard	Link	Information technology - Cloud computing - Guidance for policy development	-	-	-	-	-	-
67	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 29151	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Establishes control objectives, controls and guidelines for implementing controls, to meet the requirements identified by a risk and impact assessment related to the protection of personally identifiable information.	8/1/2017	Yes	Link	CHF166
68	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 29134	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Gives guidelines for a process on privacy impact assessments, and a structure and content of a PIA report.	6/1/2017	Yes	Link	\$108.54
69	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27002	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides a reference set of generic information security controls including implementation guidance.	2/1/2022	No	-	CHF208
70	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27003	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	ISO/IEC 27003:2017 provides explanation and guidance on ISO/IEC 27001:2013.	3/1/2017	No	-	CHF166
71	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27004	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides guidelines intended to assist organizations in evaluating the information security performance and the effectiveness of an information security management system in order to fulfil the requirements of ISO/IEC 27001:2013, 9.1.	12/1/2016	No	-	CHF187
72	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27005	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides guidance to assist organizations to: fulfil the requirements of ISO/IEC 27001 concerning actions to address information security risks; perform information security risk management activities, specifically information security risk assessment and treatment.	10/1/2022	No	-	CHF187
73	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27040	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides detailed technical guidance on how organizations can define an appropriate level of risk mitigation by employing a well-proven and consistent approach to the planning, design, documentation, and implementation of data storage security.	1/1/2015	No	-	CHF208
74	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC 27557	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Provides guidance to organizations for integrating risks related to the processing of personally identifiable information (PII) as part of an organizational privacy risk management programme.	11/1/2022	Yes	Link	CHF124
75	SENTINEL	ISO 31000:2018	Standard	Link	Risk management	ISO/TC 262	Provides guidelines on managing risk faced by organizations. The application of these guidelines can be customized to any organization and its context.	2/1/2018	Yes	Link	CHF92
76	SENTINEL	IEC 31010:2019	Standard	Link	Risk management	ISO/TC 262	Double logo standard with ISO and provides guidance on the selection and application of techniques for assessing risk in a wide range of situations.	6/1/2019	Yes	Link	CHF380
77	SENTINEL	ISO/IEC TR 27550:2019	Standard	Link	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection	JTC 1/SC 27	Provides privacy engineering guidelines that are intended to help organizations integrate recent advances in privacy engineering into system life cycle processes.	9/1/2019	No	-	CHF187

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
78	PRESERVE	EN13432	Standard	Link	Packaging - sales and grouped	EPO - Packaging - sales and grouped	-	9/1/2005	No	Link	\$0.00
79	PRESERVE	M/584	Standard	Link	Recycled Plastics	TC 249	Plastics recycling and recycled plastics	-	Yes	Link	\$81.31
80	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 261	TC	Link	PACKAGING	TC 261	Dealing with terminology, dimensions, capacities, marking, test methods, performance requirements and environmental aspects in the field of packaging and unit loads. The field covers primary, secondary and transport packagings and unit loads, whatever the materials, shapes, contents or distribution system used.	-	Yes	Link	-
81	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 249	TC	Link	PLASTICS	TC 249	Standardization of 1) terminology, 2) test methods, 3) specifications, classifications and designation systems, 4) environmental aspects, 5) joining systems and techniques, of plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products.	-	Yes	Link	-
82	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 249 WG 9	TC	Link	Characterisation of Degradability	TC 249 WG 9	Definition of terms, vocabulary and identification means regarding degradable plastics and degradability of plastics. Standardisation of test methods for the characterisation of the degradability of plastics in various environments. Standardisation of specifications for degradable plastics.	-	Yes	Link	-
83	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 249 WG 24	TC	Link	Coordination of Environmental Issues	TC 249 WG 24	Strategic aspects and coordination of all standardization activities in the field of plastics relating to environmental aspects. The focus is on, but not limited to biobased plastics, biodegradability, carbon and environmental footprint, circular economy and resource efficiency, microplastics and plastics in the environment, recycling and waste management.	-	Yes	Link	-
84	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 261 SC 4 WG 2	TC	Link	Degradability And Organic Recovery of Packaging And Packaging Materials	TC 261/SC 4/WG 2	The task of WG 2 is to produce standards for packaging and packaging materials concerning: - Definition of degradability, modes of degradability (e.g. photo - bio-chemistry - thermal - etc.), steps of degradability (e.g. fragmentation, solubilization, transformation, etc.) - Test methods of	-	Yes	Link	-
85	PRESERVE	CEN/TC 411 (WGs 1,3,4,5)	TC	Link	BIO-BASED PRODUCTS	TC 411 (WGs 1,3,4,5)	Development of standards for bio-based products covering horizontal aspects. This includes consistent terminology, sampling, certification tools, bio-based content, application of and correlation towards life cycle analysis, sustainability criteria for biomass used and for final products, and aspects where further harmonization is needed on horizontal level: i. Development of standards for bio-solvents, covering product functionality, biodegradability and, if necessary, product specific aspects not covered under 1.	-	No	-	-
86	PRESERVE	ISO/TC 61 SC 14 WG 2	TC	Link	Environmental aspects	TC 61/SC 14	All standardization activities in the field of plastics relating to environmental and sustainability aspects.	-	No	-	-
87	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC 19510	Standard	Link	Information technology	ISO/IEC JTC 1	is to provide a notation that is readily understandable by all business users, from the business analysts that create the initial drafts of the processes, to the technical developers responsible for implementing the technology that	7/1/2013	No	-	CHF208
88	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC 30141	Standard	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	This document provides a standardized IoT Reference Architecture using a common vocabulary, reusable designs and industry best practices.	8/1/2018	No	-	CHF208
89	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32	TC	Link	Data management and interchange	JTC 1/SC 32	Standards for data management within and among local and distributed information systems environments. SC 32 provides enabling technologies to promote harmonization of data management facilities across sector-specific areas.	-	No	-	-
90	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC 17789	Standard	Link	Cloud computing and distributed platforms	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Specifies the cloud computing reference architecture (CCRA).	10/1/2014	No	-	-

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
91	KITT4SME	ISO/TS 15066:2016	Standard	Link	Robotics	ISO/TC 299	Specifies safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems and the work environment, and supplements the requirements and guidance on collaborative industrial robot operation given in ISO 10218-1 and ISO 10218-2.	2/1/2016	No	-	CHF145
92	KITT4SME	ISO TC 108 SC 5	Standard	Link	Condition monitoring and diagnostics of machine systems	TC 108/SC 5	Standardization of the procedures, processes and equipment requirements uniquely related to the technical activity of condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines systems in which selected physical parameters associated with an operating machine system are periodically or continuously sensed.	-	No	-	-
93	KITT4SME	ISO TC 199	Standard	Link	Safety of machinery	TC 199	Standardization of basic concepts and general principles for safety of machinery incorporating terminology, methodologies, guards and safety devices within the framework of ISO / IEC Guide 51 and in cooperation with other ISO and IEC technical committees.	-	No	-	-
94	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	TC	Link	Artificial intelligence	JTC 1/SC 42	Standardization in the area of Artificial Intelligence. Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence.	-	No	-	-
95	KITT4SME	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	TC	Link	Internet of things and digital twin	JTC 1/SC 41	Supported administratively by IEC. All information related to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 is available on the IEC web site Standardization in the area of Internet of Things and related technologies.	-	No	-	-
96	KITT4SME	ISO 30401:2018	Standard	Link	Knowledge management systems Requirements	ISO/TC 260	Sets requirements and provides guidelines for establishing, implementing, maintaining, reviewing and improving an effective management system for knowledge management in organizations.	11/1/2018	No	-	CHF124
97	ENVISION	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
98	EnerMan	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
99	DEDICAT 6G	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
100	AutoFair	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
101	AI-PROFICIENT	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	TC	Link	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	Standardization in the area of Artificial Intelligence. Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence. Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications.	-	-	-	-
102	AI-PROFICIENT	CEN-CENELEC JTC 21	TC	Link	Artificial intelligence	CEN-CENELEC JTC 21	Produce standardization deliverables in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and related use of data, as well as provide guidance to other technical committees concerned with Artificial Intelligence.	-	-	-	-
103	AI-PROFICIENT	ISO/IEC TR 24028: 2020	Standard	Link	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	Approaches to establish trust in AI systems through transparency, explainability, controllability, etc., engineering pitfalls and typical associated threats and risks to AI systems, along with possible mitigation techniques and methods, and, approaches to assess and achieve availability, resiliency, reliability, accuracy, safety, security and privacy of AI systems	2020-05	No	-	CHF166
104	AI-PROFICIENT	ISO/IEC TR 24030:2021	Standard	Link	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	A collection of representative use cases of AI applications in a variety of domains.	2021-05	No	-	CHF208
105	AI-PROFICIENT	ISO/IEC DIS 42001	Standard	Link	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence. Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications.	2023-12	No	-	-
106	ICARUS	Standard and TC	Standard	Link	Artificial intelligence	-	-	-	-	-	-
107	H2Value	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
108	ARTEMIS	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
109	VITAL	CEN/TC 261	TC	Link	PACKAGING	CEN/TC 261	Responsible for the elaboration of standards dealing with terminology, dimensions, capacities, marking, test methods, performance requirements and environmental aspects in the field of packaging and unit loads. The field covers primary, secondary and transport packagings and unit loads, whatever the materials, shapes, contents or distribution system used.	-	-	-	-

No	Project Name	Standard and TC	Document Type	URL	Technology or Domain	Technical Committee	Abstract/Scope	Publication Date	EN	EN-URL	Price
110	VITAL	CEN/TC 249	TC	Link	PLASTICS	CEN/TC 249	Standardization of 1) terminology, 2) test methods, 3) specifications, classifications and designation systems, 4) environmental aspects, 5) joining systems and techniques, of plastics, plastic-based materials, semi-finished products and products (thermoplastics, thermosets, degradable plastics, bio-based polymers, thermoplastic elastomers, composites, reinforcement products for plastics, recyclates).	-	-	-	-
111	VITAL	ISO/TC 122	TC	Link	Packaging	ISO/TC 122	Standardization in the field of packaging with regard to terminology and definitions, characteristics, performance requirements and tests, and utilization of related technologies on packaging.	-	-	-	-
112	VITAL	ISO/TC 207	TC	Link	Environmental management	ISO/TC 207	Standardization in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.	-	-	-	-
113	VITAL	ISO/TC 323	TC	Link	Circular economy	ISO/TC 323	Standardization in the field of Circular Economy to develop frameworks, guidance, supporting tools and requirements for the implementation of activities of all involved organizations, to maximize the contribution to Sustainable Development.	-	-	-	-
114	VITAL	CEN/TC467	TC	Link	CLIMATE CHANGE	CEN/TC467	The TC addresses standardization in the field of mitigation and adaptation to climate change, including related social and economic aspects.	-	-	-	-
115	CyberSEAS	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
116	Smart Droplets	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
117	HERCULES	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
118	LOCARD	ISO/IEC WG4	TC	Link	Interconnection of information technology equipment	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25	Standardization of microprocessor systems and of interfaces and protocols for the interconnection of computer systems and computer peripheral equipment.	-	-	-	-
119	LOCARD	ISO 2865:1973	Standard	Link	Materials for the production of primary aluminium	ISO/TC 226	Aluminium oxide primarily used for the production of aluminium	1973-12	Yes	Link	CHF40
120	LOCARD	ISO 2864:1974	Standard	Link	Interchangeable magnetic six-disk pack	ISO/IEC JTC 1	Determination of boron content Curcumin spectrophotometric method. Defines the physical and magnetic characteristics for interchange of magnetic six-disk packs in order to facilitate the interchange of data between electronic data processing systems. Does not apply to a specific design. It defines only the parameters relevant for interchange.	1974-4	Yes	Link	\$61.22
121	VALUECARE	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
122	Policy Cloud	ISO/IEC-JTC1	TC	Link	Information technology	ISO/IEC JTC 1	Standardization in the field of information technology.	-	-	-	-
123	NEXUS-NESS	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
124	CPSoSaware	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-
125	eSIF-Lab	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	No	-	-
126	IMPETUS	Standard and TC	Standard	-	Involving in standardisation	-	-	-	-	-	-

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